

1 **Genome-informed design of a LAMP assay for the specific detection of the strain of**
2 **'*Candidatus Phytoplasma P. asteris*' phytoplasma occurring in grapevines in South Africa**

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23

24 **Abstract**

25

26 Grapevine yellows is one of the most damaging phytoplasma-associated diseases worldwide. It is
27 linked to several phytoplasma species, which can vary regionally due to phytoplasma and insect-
28 vector diversity. Specific, rapid and reliable detection of the grapevine yellows pathogen has an
29 important role in phytoplasma control. The purpose of this study was to develop and validate a
30 specific LAMP assay for detection of a distinct strain of grapevine ‘*Candidatus Phytoplasma*
31 *asteri*’ that is present in South Africa, through implementation of a genome-informed test design
32 approach. Several freely available, user-friendly, web-based tools were coupled to design the
33 specific LAMP assays. The criteria for selection of the assays were set for each step of the process,
34 which resulted in four experimentally operative LAMP assays that targeted *ftsH/hflB* gene region,
35 specific to the aster yellows phytoplasma strain from South Africa. A real-time PCR was
36 developed, targeting the same genetic region, to provide extensive validation of the LAMP assay.
37 The validated molecular assays are highly specific to the targeted aster yellows phytoplasma strain
38 from South African, with good sensitivity and reproducibility. We show a genome-informed
39 molecular test design and an efficient validation approach for molecular tests if reference and
40 sample materials are sparse and hard to obtain.

41

42

43 **Keywords:** phytoplasma, aster yellows, molecular detection, LAMP

44

45 **Introduction**

46

47 Grapevine yellows (GY) is a disease of *Vitis vinifera* associated with several phytoplasmas that is
48 present in grapevine-growing regions throughout the world, and that can lead to severe yield losses
49 (Dermastia et al. 2017). The epidemiological cycles of GY show regional variations due to
50 diversity of phytoplasma species and insect vector diversity (Bertaccini et al. 2014).

51 In South Africa, symptoms of GY were observed for the first time in 2006 (Botti and
52 Bertaccini 2006). The main pathogen that causes GY in South African is an aster yellows
53 phytoplasma strain (Aster yellows from South Africa AY-SA) classified within the 16SrI-B
54 subgroup, which correspond to '*Candidatus* Phytoplasma asteris' (Engelbrecht et al. 2010;
55 Carstens et al. 2011). This pathogen was first confirmed in vineyards in South Africa in the
56 Vredendal region of the Olifantsriver Valley (Engelbrecht et al. 2010), and has since been reported
57 in the wine-producing regions of Waboomsrivier, and Robertson (Carstens, 2014). As well as its
58 main host *Vitis vinifera*, AY-SA have been detected in various species of wild and crop plants that
59 grow in the vicinity of vineyards (Kruger et al. 2015). These phytoplasmas are transmitted by a
60 leafhopper indigenous to South Africa, *Mgenia fuscovaria* (Kruger et al. 2018). The common
61 symptoms of GY often lead to abortion of immature berries (Engelbrecht et al. 2010), and
62 consequently result in high yield losses, which can reach 30% for certain grapevine cultivars
63 (Constable and Bertaccini 2017; Carstens 2014).

64 Knowledge gaps in the disease cycles of GY remain, with the need for specific, rapid, and
65 reliable detection of the pathogen, preferably in an on-site setting. Loop-mediated isothermal
66 amplification (LAMP) is among the promising methods for detection of phytoplasmas. This
67 molecular method generates high quantities of amplified DNA from a specific DNA fragment

68 using a set of four to six primers (Notomi et al. 2000). The advantages of LAMP include isothermal
69 amplification that does not require expensive apparatus, speed, and high resilience to various
70 inhibitors present in samples (e.g. see Kaneko et al. 2007; Hara-Kudo et al. 2007; Wang et al.
71 2009; Zhang et al. 2013). These characteristics allow detection of pathogenic bacteria in the field,
72 including phytoplasmas, with minimum sample preparation (Kogovšek et al. 2015, 2017). LAMP
73 tests have already been developed for universal detection of different phytoplasmas of the 16Sr
74 groups (Tomlinson et al. 2010; Bekele et al. 2011; Kogovšek et al. 2015; Dickinson 2015). A
75 LAMP test that was designed for the detection of grapevine “flavescence dorée” phytoplasmas
76 was paired with a sample homogenization procedure for grapevine samples (leaf vein, flower, or
77 berry) that allows direct testing of crude homogenates in LAMP assays, with sensitivity on par
78 with quantitative PCR (Kogovšek et al. 2015, 2017).

79 The purpose of the present study was to develop and validate a LAMP assay for specific
80 detection of the GY phytoplasma in South Africa (i.e., AY-SA). No adequate LAMP assays could
81 be designed based on commonly used phytoplasma target sequences (data not shown), and
82 therefore we exploited the available genomic data to identify novel diagnostic markers and to
83 develop LAMP and real-time PCR assays for specific detection of AY-SA. The LAMP test was
84 then validated in-house and in an inter-laboratory test performance study.

85

86 **Materials and methods**

87

88 ***In-silico* identification of novel diagnostic markers**

89 Automated analysis was carried out using a freely available program for rapid identification of
90 PCR primers for unique core sequences: RUCS (Thomsen et al. 2017). RUCS was thus used to

91 identify genome sequences specific to the AY-SA; namely, two draft assemblies of AY-SA
92 genome that consisted of 16 and 550 contigs. Assemblies were refined and combined in a complete
93 genome sequence (GenBank accession number CP035949), and later published by Coetzee et al.
94 (2019). The negative dataset (Supplementary Table S1) provides complete or draft genome
95 sequences of other phytoplasmas (18 genomes) and mycoplasmas (55 genomes) from publically
96 available databases (see Supplementary Table S1 for NCBI/GenBank accession numbers).

97

98 **Design of LAMP and real-time PCR assays**

99 The novel diagnostic markers identified by RUCS (Thomsen et al. 2017) were filtered based on
100 their suitability for the test design, in terms of length of at least 200 bp, and sequence uniqueness
101 confirmed by blastn (Altschul et al. 1990). Altogether, three suitable unique sequences were
102 selected, and are indicated as Seq1, Seq3, and Seq11. LAMP primer sets were designed using the
103 PrimerExplorer V5 software (Eiken Genome, [http://primerexplorer.jp /lampv5e/index.html](http://primerexplorer.jp/lampv5e/index.html)), and
104 the primers and hydrolysis probe for real-time PCR were designed using Primer Express version
105 2.0 (Applied Biosystems). The LAMP primer design was run with the default parameters adapted
106 to AT-rich template sequences, since all target sequences had very low GC content (18% – 35%).
107 The following modifications were implemented: the lengths of the F2/B2 and F3/B3 primers were
108 adapted to 15 bp – 25 bp; and the GC rate was expanded to 25% – 65%. The proposed LAMP
109 assays were checked manually and filtered using mainly the following pre-defined minimum
110 quality parameter criteria: (i) dG of the 3' end at region F2, the 5' end at region F1c, the 3' end at
111 region B2, and the 5' end at region B1c lower than -4.0 kcal/mol; (ii) T_m differences among the
112 primer pairs was <3 °C; and (iii) the high specificity of each primer (i.e., F3, B3, F2, B2, F1c, B1c)
113 was confirmed by the BLAST program.

114 The quality of the designed oligonucleotides was checked *in-silico* using Oligo Analyser
115 (Integrated DNA Technologies), and the specificities of the primers and probes were evaluated *in-*
116 *silico* using blastn (Altschul et al. 1990) (Figure 1).

117

118 **Material for test evaluations**

119 ***Synthetic reference material***

120 The synthetic double-stranded (ds)DNAs were based on the unique genomic sequences of Seq1,
121 Seq3, and Seq11 (Supplementary Table S2). These were synthesized commercially (gBlock Gene
122 Fragments, Integrated DNA Technologies) and used to prepare defined concentrations of the target
123 DNAs in TE buffer (Sigma-Aldrich) with salmon sperm DNA (final concentration, 25 mg/ml).
124 Absolute concentrations of the target copy numbers were determined using digital PCR with the
125 set of primers and probe of the AY-SA_ftsH real-time PCR assay. Synthetic reference material
126 was used to optimize the LAMP tests, and preparation of defined spiked grapevine leaf vein
127 extracts were used for evaluation of different on-site sample preparation techniques.

128

129 ***Phytoplasma collection***

130 The specificities of the designed PCR and LAMP tests were determined on DNA from an
131 international phytoplasma collection (Paltrinieri et al. 2015). Altogether, 21 different
132 phytoplasmas were tested that belonged to the 16Sr group: 16SrI-A, 16SrI-B (7), 16SrI-C, 16SrI-
133 F, 16SrII-C, 16SrIII-A, 16SrIII-B (2), 16SrVII-A, 16SrIX-C, 16SrX-A, 16SrXII-A (4) (
134 Table 1). All phytoplasma strains were propagated in periwinkle, except CH1 that was propagated
135 in the original host (
136 Table 1).

137

138 ***Plant material***

139 Plant material was collected from naturally infected and healthy grapevines over the 2016 to 2018
140 growing seasons in South Africa. Grapevines from a commercial vineyard (cultivar ‘Colombar’)
141 in the Vredendal region of the Western Cape (South Africa) were selected based on their
142 symptomatology. The selection and preparation of the grapevine samples was described in Van
143 der Vyver et al. (2019). The grapevines included in the analysis were selected based on their visual
144 symptomatology in February 2016. Out of 49 grapevines chosen for this study, 37 were
145 symptomatic and 12 did not show any phytoplasma symptoms (Van der Vyver et al. 2019).
146 Altogether, 114 grapevine samples were collected at four different times from 2016 to 2018 (Table
147 3Table 4). DNA from the grapevine samples was extracted from phloem scrapings using the CTAB
148 method, as described by Van der Vyver et al. (2019). The grapevine samples were divided in two
149 groups, as symptomatic and asymptomatic, based on their symptom expression in 2016. The
150 presence of AY was confirmed using AY nested PCR (Van der Vyver et al., 2019).

151 Six carrot samples (*Daucus carota* subsp. *sativus*) with symptoms of an AY infection were
152 obtained in Slovenia in 2017 (

153 Table 1, Mehle et al., 2018). The DNA was extracted and purified using magnetic-bead-
154 based plant DNA kits (QuickPick SML; Bio-Nobile, Turku, Finland) on an automated DNA
155 purification system (KingFisher mL; Thermo Labsystem), as described previously (Pirc et al.
156 2009), and with a minor modification (440 µl lysate used in the purification). The presence of AY
157 was confirmed using diagnostic real-time PCR (Christensen et al. 2004; Angelini et al. 2007;
158 Nikolić et al. 2009).

159 On-site homogenization was tested using grapevine leaf veins spiked with target DNA.
160 Two types of on-site sample preparation were tested: a dipstick method, and a direct homogenate
161 method. The dipstick method was performed accordingly to Zou et al. (2017), with minor
162 modifications. Here, the leaf veins were homogenized manually with vigorous shaking for 2 min
163 in cell lysis buffer (20 mM Tris, pH 8.0, 25 mM NaCl, 2.5 mM Na₂EDTA, 0.05% sodium dodecyl
164 sulfate) in 4.5-ml tall prep A lysing matrix tubes (Matrix A; MP Biomedical). For the direct
165 homogenate technique, leaf veins were homogenized manually with vigorous shaking with ELISA
166 buffer (264 mM Tris, 236 mM Tris-HCl, 137 mM NaCl, 2% polyvinylpyrrolidone K-25, 2 mM
167 polyethylene glycol 6000, 0.05% Tween 20, pH 8.2) for 2 min in 4.5-ml tall prep A lysing matrix
168 tubes (Matrix A; MP Biomedical). The homogenate was diluted 10-fold in molecular grade water
169 (Top-Bio) and tested directly in the LAMP and real-time PCR assays.

170

171 **Loop-mediated isothermal amplification**

172 The LAMP reactions were performed on a sequence detection system (QuantStudio 3 and
173 QuantStudio 7 Flex real-time PCR systems; Applied Biosystems, ThermoFisher Scientific), and/or
174 using portable 8-well strips LAMP detection system (Genie II; OptiGene).

175 Optimization of the assays was conducted for four assays that gave promising results in the
176 preliminary experimental evaluation. In the optimization step, the following LAMP conditions
177 were varied: reaction temperature; concentration of inner primers; concentration of Mg²⁺ ions; and
178 form of synthetic target DNA (denatured, double stranded). To determine the best primer
179 concentration, three different forward inner primer (FIP) and backward inner primer (BIP)
180 concentrations were tested: 0.8 μM, 1.2 μM, and 1.6 μM, without and with the addition of 2 mM
181 Mg²⁺ ions (Supplementary File S1).

182 The optimized LAMP AY-SA_ftsH assay (fNegative real-time PCR reaction after 45

183 cycles

184 gNegative LAMP reaction after 30 min

185

186 Table 2) used a reaction volume of 25 μ l that contained (final concentrations): 0.2 μ M F3
187 and B3 primers (Sigma Aldrich, Integrated DNA Technologies), 1.6 μ M HPLC-purified FIP and
188 BIP primers (Sigma Aldrich, Integrated DNA Technologies), 1 \times isothermal master mix ISO-001
189 (OptiGene), and 5 μ l sample. When the LAMP reaction was performed on the instruments that
190 required a reference dye (i.e., QuantStudio 3 and QuantStudio 7 Flex real-time PCR systems),
191 ROX dye was added to the reaction (final concentration 0.1 \times ; Premix Ex Taq, Takara and Kapa
192 Probe Fast qPCR Master Mix; KapaBiosystems). The LAMP assay was conducted under
193 isothermal conditions at 63 $^{\circ}$ C for 30 min (except where stated otherwise). The isothermal reaction
194 followed the measurement of the melting temperature (T_m) by heating the reaction to 98 $^{\circ}$ C and
195 cooling to 60 $^{\circ}$ C (ramp, 0.05 $^{\circ}$ C/s). The data were analyzed using the QuantStudio real-time PCR
196 software v1.3, or the QuantStudio Design and Analysis desktop software v1.5.1 (Applied
197 Biosystems, ThermoFisher Scientific), with automatic baseline and a manual threshold of 0.3. Data
198 from the portable 8-well strips (Genie II; OptiGene) was analyzed automatically by the instrument
199 software. A positive reaction was defined by a curve of sigmoidal shape above the background, a
200 time of positivity <30 min, and a T_m from 80 $^{\circ}$ C to 83 $^{\circ}$ C.

201 The optimized test was validated and evaluated for the following matrices: (i) serial dilution
202 of heat-denatured synthetic target dsDNA (concentration range, 10^8 to 10^2 target molecules/ml);
203 (ii) phytoplasma DNA from the phytoplasma collection (Paltrinieri et al. 2015); (iii) carrot samples
204 from Slovenia; and (iv) grapevine samples from South Africa. Some natural samples and
205 phytoplasma DNA from the phytoplasma collection were tested as 10-fold dilutions, due to the
206 limited quantities of the samples.

207 The stability of the reaction mixture was tested for the optimized LAMP AY-SA_ftsH
208 assay. The reaction mixture was incubated at 30 $^{\circ}$ C for 0 h, 3 h, and 6 h in closed tubes. After the

209 incubation, the synthetic target dsDNA (dilutions, 10^7 to 10^2 target molecules/ml) was added to
210 the reaction mixture, and the LAMP reaction was performed.

211

212 **Real-time PCR**

213 The real-time PCR assay with AY-SA_ftsH (fNegative real-time PCR reaction after 45 cycles

214 gNegative LAMP reaction after 30 min

215

216 Table 2) targets the same *ftsH* gene as the LAMP AY-SA_ftsH assay. All of the real-time PCR
217 reactions were performed in triplicate (QuantStudio 3 and QuantStudio 7 Flex real-time PCR
218 systems; Applied Biosystems, ThermoFisher Scientific) using the following universal cycling
219 conditions: 2 min at 50 °C, 10 min at 95 °C, followed by 45 cycles of 15 s at 95 °C, and 1 min at
220 60 °C, using standard temperature ramping mode. The reaction volume of 10 µl contained (final
221 concentrations): 900 nM primers, 200 nM 6-carboxyfluorescein (FAM) and black hole quencher
222 (BHQ)-1 labeled probes (all Integrated DNA Technologies), 1× TaqMan Universal PCR Master
223 Mix (Applied Biosystems, ThermoFisher Scientific), and 1 µl or 2 µl sample DNA. The real-time
224 PCR data were analyzed using the QuantStudio real-time PCR software v1.3 or the QuantStudio
225 Design and Analysis desktop software v1.5.1 (Applied Biosystems, ThermoFisher Scientific), with
226 automatic baseline and a manual threshold of 0.04. The real-time PCR data are given as C_q values
227 (i.e., real-time PCR quantification cycles).

228 The presence of phytoplasma DNA in the samples was confirmed by universal real-time
229 PCR assays for phytoplasmas, as described by Christensen et al. (2004). The test was performed
230 as described for real-time PCR AY-SA_ftsH assay, with the following modifications (final
231 concentrations): forward primer, 300 nM; reverse primer, 900 nM; and FAM and BHQ-1 labeled
232 probe, 100 nM. The real-time PCR data analysis parameters included an automated baseline and a
233 manual threshold of 0.02.

234

235 **Digital PCR**

236 For digital PCR (QX100 Droplet Digital PCR system; Bio-Rad, Pleasanton, CA, USA), the real-
237 time PCR AY-SA_ftsH assay (fNegative real-time PCR reaction after 45 cycles

238 ^gNegative LAMP reaction after 30 min

239

240 Table 2) was transferred to digital PCR format and used to determine the concentration of the
241 target copy numbers in the test items and controls. The reactions contained 12 μ l dPCR Supermix
242 for probes (Bio-Rad) and 8 μ L sample DNA, with the primer and probe concentrations of 900
243 nmol (each primer) and 200 nmol per reaction, respectively. After droplet generation, 40 μ l of the
244 generated droplet emulsion was transferred to a new 96-well PCR plate (Eppendorf) and amplified
245 in a thermal cycler (Bio-Rad). The amplification conditions were 10 min DNA polymerase
246 activation at 95 °C, followed by 45 cycles of a two-step thermal profile of 15 s at 95 °C for
247 denaturation, and 60 s at 60 °C for annealing and extension, followed by a final hold of 10 min at
248 98 °C for droplet stabilization, and cooling to 4 °C. The temperature ramp rate was set to 3 °C/s,
249 and the lid was heated to 105 °C, according to the manufacturer's recommendations. After the
250 thermal cycling, the plates were transferred to a droplet reader (QX100; Bio-Rad). The software
251 package provided with the digital PCR system was used for data acquisition (QuantaSoft, version
252 17.4.0917; Bio-Rad). A minimum of 10,000 accepted droplets per reaction was required for the
253 reaction to be considered valid, and no nonvalid reactions were observed. A fixed manual global
254 threshold that discriminated between negative and positive droplets was selected. A reaction was
255 interpreted as positive if the number of positive droplets was ≥ 3 . Positive and no-template controls
256 were used in each run. Each sample was analyzed as three technical repeats. The expanded
257 measurement uncertainty was calculated for each sample.

258

259 **Validation of new LAMP and real-time PCR**

260 Validations were conducted following the European and Mediterranean Plant Protection
261 Organization guidelines on validation (EPPO 2018), which include analytical specificity,

262 analytical sensitivity, diagnostic specificity and sensitivity, repeatability, reproducibility, and
263 robustness (

264 Figure 2**Error! Reference source not found.**)

265 The analytical specificity was evaluated on synthetic DNA, phytoplasma DNA from the
266 phytoplasma collection (Paltrinieri et al. 2015), and the carrot samples from Slovenia (

267 Table 1). The presence of phytoplasma DNA in the samples was confirmed, and the
268 concentrations were determined by the universal real-time PCR assays for phytoplasmas
269 (Christensen et al. 2004).

270 The analytical sensitivity of the designed LAMP AY-SA_ftsH and the real-time PCR AY-
271 SA_ftsH assays were determined on 10-fold serial dilutions of synthetic target DNA sequences
272 (Supplementary Table S2), as 10^8 to 10^1 target molecules/ml. Each dilution was tested in two
273 replicates and on two instruments (QuantStudio 3 and QuantStudio 7 Flex real-time PCR systems;
274 Applied Biosystems, ThermoFisher Scientific; and Genie II; OptiGene), and in three replicates
275 and two instruments (QuantStudio 3 and QuantStudio 7 Flex real-time PCR systems; Applied
276 Biosystems, ThermoFisher Scientific) for the LAMP AY-SA_ftsH and real-time PCR AY-
277 SA_ftsH assays, respectively.

278 Diagnostic sensitivity and specificity were assessed on a collection of infected and healthy
279 grapevine samples collected from 2016 to 2018 (Table 4). The samples were collected within the
280 study described by Van der Vyver et al. (2019) and the presence of phytoplasma DNA in the
281 grapevine samples was tested with nested PCR. Some DNA samples isolated from symptomatic
282 grapevines were diluted 10-fold in molecular grade water due to limited sample quantities. The
283 DNA samples from asymptomatic grapevines were tested in an undiluted form. The samples were
284 tested by LAMP AY-SA_ftsH and real-time PCR AY-SA_ftsH assay, along with the universal

285 real-time PCR assay for phytoplasmas (Christensen et al. 2004). Both real-time PCR assays were
286 performed in duplicates, and the LAMP assay in single reaction. Molecular grade water was used
287 as no template control and synthetic target DNA as positive amplification control in every
288 experiment. The cross-reactivity of the designed LAMP and real-time PCR assays with the plant
289 tissue, its microflora, and other phytoplasmas was monitored by testing a total of 114 grapevine
290 DNA extracts. Diagnostic sensitivity and specificity were evaluated in terms of the grapevine
291 symptomatology, the AY nested PCR (results from the study described by Van der Vyver et al.
292 2019), and the universal real-time PCR assay for phytoplasmas (Christensen et al. 2004) .

293 Repeatability was analyzed across triplicates of an assay for the real-time PCR, and as
294 duplicates for the LAMP assay (i.e., within run). Reproducibility was determined across two
295 repeated day assays (i.e., between runs), between two different laboratories, between two detection
296 systems for real-time PCR (QuantStudio 3 and QuantStudio 7 Flex real-time PCR systems;
297 Applied Biosystems, ThermoFisher Scientific), and between three detection systems for LAMP
298 (QuantStudio 3 and QuantStudio 7 Flex real-time PCR systems; Applied Biosystems,
299 ThermoFisher Scientific; and Genie II; OptiGene). For the assessment of repeatability and
300 reproducibility, a standard curve of the synthetic target DNA was used (analytical sensitivity).
301 Reproducibility of the LAMP assay was additionally assessed in a test performance study (TPS).

302

303 **Test performance study**

304 The performance of the LAMP_AY-SA_ftsH assay was evaluated in the TPS. The TPS sample
305 panel was composed of 12 test items: positive samples containing synthetic dsDNA of AY-SA;
306 positive samples containing samples naturally contaminated with AY-SA; and negative samples
307 containing other AY or host-plant *Vitis vinifera* DNA, with the corresponding control samples.

308 Qualitative reference values were assigned to the test items based on the results of the LAMP AY-
309 SA_ftsH assay. Quantitative reference values (target concentrations) were determined using digital
310 PCR analysis of the test items and controls. Stability of the test items and controls was tested with
311 the LAMP AY-SA_ftsH assay. The stability testing was carried out under conditions that
312 mimicked transport and storage conditions (< -15 °C).

313 The data for each participating laboratory were analyzed based on the numbers of positive
314 agreements (as positive detected from positive expected), negative agreements (as negative
315 detected from negative expected), positive deviations (as positive detected from negative
316 expected), and negative deviations (as negative detected from positive expected). All of the
317 samples were analyzed in two separate reactions by each participant. A sample was considered
318 positive if it produced at least one positive reaction, according to the exponential amplification
319 profile, the time of positivity < 30 min, and the T_m from 82 °C to 83 °C.

320 Analysis of the collected TPS results was based on the concordance with the assigned
321 reference values (Supplementary File S2).

322

323 **Adaptation of LAMP for on-site use**

324 Two different on-site sample preparation methods were tested: a dipstick method and direct use of
325 a crude homogenate. The nucleic acid purification using the dipsticks method was performed
326 according to Zou et al. (2017), with the following modifications: (i) the size of the nucleic acid
327 binding active zone was 3 mm \times 3 mm; (ii) the grapevine leaf veins (~200 mg) were added to a
328 TallPrep Lysing Matrix A 4.5-ml tube (MP Biomedicals) that contained 1 ml cell lysis buffer; (iii)
329 the grapevine tissue was macerated by shaking the tube for approximately 2 min; and (iv) the
330 prepared homogenate was spiked with synthetic target DNA or isolated AY-SA DNA. The nucleic

331 acids from the dipstick were eluted directly into the LAMP reaction or into the real-time PCR mix
332 using pre-added molecular grade water for the sample volume. Direct use of crude homogenates
333 was tested as described by Kogovšek et al. (2015), using ELISA buffer and grapevine leaf veins.
334 The prepared homogenate was spiked with synthetic target DNA or isolated AY-SA DNA. The
335 dipstick cell lysis buffer and the ELISA buffer were spiked with the synthetic target DNA sequence
336 to final concentrations of 10^7 to 10^4 DNA molecules/ml, or with the DNA isolate of sample
337 S40N16 to a final concentration of $\sim 8 \times 10^4$ genomes/ml. Both of these sample preparation methods
338 were evaluated for use with the LAMP and real-time PCR assays.

339 The stability of the DNA and the possibility for short-term storage using the dipstick
340 approach was tested by adding the following steps to the method described: the dipsticks were
341 placed in new 2-ml centrifuge tubes after the wash step; the dipsticks were dried at room
342 temperature (22 ± 1 °C) in the open centrifuge tubes for 30 min; and the dried dipsticks were stored
343 in the closed centrifuge tubes in the dark at room temperature. The stability of the target DNA on
344 these stored dipsticks was tested after 3 weeks, with the LAMP assay. The dipsticks were first
345 briefly dipped into 100 μ l wash buffer (to rehydrate the dipstick nucleic acid binding zone), and
346 were then eluted directly into the LAMP reaction mixture.

347

348 **Statistical analysis**

349 Nonlinear modeling of the probability of detection of the target was calculated in the R statistical
350 environment (R Core Team 2020) using the *drc* package (Ritz et al. 2015), along with
351 determination of the target concentration that was detected with 95% probability (LOD_{95}).
352 Dichotomous positive and negative results from the LAMP and real-time PCR assays were
353 analyzed using a 2×2 contingency table.

354

355 **Results**

356

357 **Design of the LAMP and real-time PCR assays**

358 The sequence analysis tool RUCS (Thomsen et al. 2017) was applied to the 75 selected genomes,
359 which resulted in the identification of 802 sequences unique to the AY-SA genome. The great
360 majority (99%) of these specific sequences identified were shorter than 200 bp. In the range
361 suitable for LAMP design (i.e., 200-700 nucleotides), 11 sequences were identified, and these were
362 used as target sequences (Figure 3). The unique sequences of all lengths were distributed
363 throughout the AY genome.

364 All target sequences had very low GC content (18%-35%), and therefore the LAMP primer
365 design was run with the default parameters adapted to AT-rich template sequences, with the
366 implementation of the following modifications: the lengths of the F2/B2 and F3/B3 primers were
367 adapted to 15 bp - 25 bp; and the GC rate was expanded to 25% - 65%. The proposed LAMP
368 assays were checked manually and filtered using mainly the following pre-defined minimum
369 quality parameter criteria: (i) dG of the 3' end at region F2, the 5' end at region F1c, the 3' end at
370 region B2, and the 5' end at region B1c lower than -4.0 kcal/mol; (ii) T_m differences among the
371 primer pairs was <3 °C; and (iii) the high specificity of each primer (i.e., F3, B3, F2, B2, F1c, B1c)
372 was confirmed by the BLAST program. The LAMP primers of sufficient quality were successfully
373 designed on three of the 11 selected target sequences, as Seq1, Seq3, and Seq11 (Supplementary
374 Table S3). Altogether, 20 assays were selected for experimental evaluation (Supplementary Table
375 S4), of which eight primer sets were developed on Seq1, five on Seq3, and seven on Seq11
376 (Supplementary Table S3). The selected sequences were associated to their corresponding genes

377 based on the annotated genome. Seq1 and Seq3 represent partial regions of the same hypothetical
378 protein, while Seq1 1 represents a sequence linked to the cell-division protein FtsH.

379 The real-time PCR assays were developed on the target sequence that successfully
380 produced the functional LAMP primer sets. The assays were successfully developed using default
381 design parameters, to provide the specific TaqMan real-time PCR assay (fNegative real-time PCR
382 reaction after 45 cycles

383 gNegative LAMP reaction after 30 min

384

385 Table 2).

386

387 **Performances of the LAMP and real-time PCR assays**

388 *Optimization of the LAMP assays*

389 Twenty LAMP primer sets were tested empirically on synthetic target and non-target dsDNA at
390 the three different reaction temperatures of 60 °C, 62 °C, and 65 °C. Four LAMP assays that
391 successfully detected target DNA with no cross-reactivity were selected for optimization
392 (Supplementary File S1). The other assays tested did not produce any positive signals or show
393 evident cross-reactivity with non-target DNA and/or the LAMP reagents (Supplementary File S1).

394 The shortest detection time was at the reaction temperature of 62 °C for all of the specific
395 assays, and therefore the optimization step was performed at this reaction temperature. In the
396 further testing, it was noted that the LAMP assay performance and reaction characteristics did not
397 change if the reaction temperature was 62 °C or 63 °C. Hence, validation of the LAMP assay
398 developed was performed at 63 °C, to allow the combination of the runs with the assays for general
399 phytoplasma detection and for identification of different 16Sr groups described by Dickinson
400 (2015).

401 The optimal LAMP reaction mix conditions identified in the optimization step used 1.6 µM
402 FIP and BIP primers (final concentration) without addition of Mg²⁺ ions. Throughout the
403 optimization of the LAMP assay, LAMP AY-SA_ftsH assay produced the best performance
404 characteristics, and was therefore chosen for validation.

405

406 *Analytical specificity*

407 The specificity of the LAMP assay developed was tested on synthetic nontarget dsDNA, carrot
408 samples with symptoms of AY infection, and phytoplasma DNA from the phytoplasma collection
409 (Paltrinieri et al. 2015) (Table 1). AY-SA-specific LAMP did not give positive results with any of these sample materials.
410 Also, 21 different phytoplasma isolates from the phytoplasma collection were tested, which
411 corresponded to the 16Sr groups 16SrI-A, 16SrI-B (7 isolates), 16SrI-C, 16SrI-F, 16SrII-C,
412 16SrIII-A, 16SrIII-B (2 isolates), 16SrVII-A, 16SrIX-C, 16SrX-A, and 16SrXII-A (4 isolates).
413 None of the isolates represented AY-SA. All of the tested phytoplasma isolates were negative
414 using both the LAMP and the real-time PCR AY-SA-specific assays, which confirmed high
415 specificity of the tests for the variety of the 16SrI-B subgroup from South Africa. The amounts of
416 DNA in the phytoplasma samples were confirmed using the universal real-time PCR assay
417 (Christensen et al. 2004). The DNA concentration of the isolates was high ($C_q < 20$), and therefore
418 the negative results recorded with the specific LAMP assay did not arise due to low target
419 concentrations. No cross reactivity with any of the host plant DNAs was detected for either of the
420 assays tested (Table 1).

423

424 *Analytical sensitivity*

425 The analytical sensitivity was assessed on dilution of synthetic target dsDNA (Supplementary
426 **Error! Reference source not found.**). The LAMP assay showed very high sensitivity. With
427 LOD_{100} defined as the lowest target amount that gave positive results in all the parallel reactions,
428 this was 10^4 target dsDNA molecules/ml; the LOD_{95} was 8.2×10^3 target dsDNA molecules /ml

429 (Supplementary **Error! Reference source not found.**). These calculations were based on pure
430 solutions of synthetic target DNA without any plant matrix background.

431

432 ***Diagnostic specificity and sensitivity***

433 The performance parameters of the tests (Table 5) were calculated based on the sanitary status of
434 the grapevines, the results of the universal phytoplasma real-time PCR (Christensen et al. 2004),
435 and the results of the AY nested PCR (Van der Vyver et al. 2019) (Table 3 and Table 4). The
436 performance parameters in terms of the sanitary status of the grapevines were determined on 49
437 grapevine samples collected in 2016, as the sanitation status of the grapevines was not recorded
438 for the later samples. The LAMP assay showed up to 27% lower sensitivity in comparison with
439 the other tests; however, it was very specific (100% specificity). The overall accuracy was
440 adequate for the purpose of the designed test.

441 Correlations between the LAMP time of positivity and the corresponding T_m of the
442 amplification products showed that samples with lower time of positivity produced amplification
443 products with higher T_m , and *vice versa* (

444 Figure 4). The amplification products produced showed T_m from 82.2 °C to 83.2 °C. The
445 samples and controls with time of positivity <23 min generally had T_m >82.6 °C, and the samples
446 with higher time of positivity melted at <82.6 °C.

447

448 ***Repeatability and reproducibility***

449 Repeatability and reproducibility of both assays was assessed on synthetic target material (i.e., the
450 analytical sensitivity) in two different laboratories and using different laboratory equipment (e.g.,
451 pipettes, detection systems). The analysis of precision within the duplicates and across two runs

452 showed 100% agreement at 10^4 target dsDNA molecules/ml. Below 10^4 target dsDNA molecules
453 /ml, agreement varied across the different concentrations and different instruments. Considering
454 the reproducibility between runs using different detection instruments and laboratory equipment,
455 there were no effects on the reproducibility of the results. Here, 100% reproducibility was
456 maintained above LOD_{100} . Additionally, the reproducibility of the LAMP assay was assessed in
457 the TPS. The TPS results demonstrated reproducibility of the LAMP assay on all of the types of
458 test material.

459

460 ***Robustness***

461 The temperature stability of the LAMP assay reaction mixture was tested to evaluate the ease of
462 use for on-site testing. The LAMP reaction mixture gradually lost its activity over time. Incubation
463 at 30 °C resulted in gradual loss of the reagent mixture activity. After 6 h incubation, the reagent
464 mixture gave no positive reaction signal in the positive control (data not shown). However, no
465 false-positive results were observed for any of the times tested.

466 The robustness of the LAMP assay was assessed in terms of small temperature variations
467 of the isothermal reaction. The reaction temperatures tested (62, 63 °C) did not influence the results
468 of the LAMP reaction. Neither time of positivity nor T_m of the samples tested changed.

469

470 ***Test performance study***

471 Two laboratories took part in the TPS to evaluate the specific LAMP AY-SA_ftsH assay. Both
472 laboratories used identical reagents and instruments, as the isothermal master mix ISO-001
473 (OptiGene) and Genie II (OptiGene) instruments. The TPS sample panel was composed of
474 synthetic target dsDNA, grapevine samples infected with AY-SA, and negative samples containing

475 other GY phytoplasmas or host-plant *Vitis vinifera* DNA. The controls provided with the test panel
476 were used for the quality check of the dataset. If the results of the controls were concordant with
477 the expected results, the test panel data were considered as valid. All TPS results were valid, and
478 in 100% concordance with the expected results. The TPS confirmed that the LAMP AY-SA_ftsH
479 assay does not cross-react with other GY phytoplasmas or host-plant DNA, and that it is very
480 sensitive and reproducible. The detailed results of the TPS are presented in Supplementary File
481 S2.

482

483 ***Real-time PCR***

484 The AY-SA-specific real-time PCR was developed as a control assay for the LAMP assay, to
485 enable more comprehensive evaluation of the LAMP assay and sample material used in the
486 validation process. Real-time PCR was validated on the same material and in parallel with the
487 LAMP assay. Like the LAMP assay, the real-time PCR showed 100% analytical specificity for all
488 of the sample material tested. The analytical sensitivity of the real-time PCR was very close to the
489 sensitivity of the LAMP assay. The LOD₁₀₀ was the same for both assays, at 10⁴ target dsDNA
490 molecules/ml, although the LOD₉₅ was slightly different for the real-time PCR assay, at 6.8 × 10³
491 target dsDNA molecules/ml (Supplementary **Error! Reference source not found.**). The
492 diagnostic specificity of the real-time PCR was in line with the LAMP assay. However, real-time
493 PCR showed greater diagnostic sensitivity, at >90%. Consequently, the overall accuracy of the
494 real-time PCR was approximately 21% higher compared to the LAMP assay. The repeatability of
495 the real-time PCR was assessed within triplicates and between two runs, and showed 100%
496 agreement at 10⁴ target dsDNA molecules/ml, as had the LAMP assay. Similarly, the
497 reproducibility of the real-time PCR assay was the same as that of the LAMP assay.

498 The concordance of the results between the two tests was 92% (104 concordant/113);
499 however, the discrepancies were mainly observed for the samples analyzed as 10-fold dilutions in
500 the LAMP assay (Table 3Table 4), which provided one tenth the sensitivity of the LAMP assay on
501 natural samples, in comparison to the real-time PCR. Considering only the results of the undiluted
502 samples, the sensitivities of the AY-SA-specific LAMP and the real-time PCR were similar (2
503 discrepancies/81), as determined for the analytical sensitivity. However, no correlation was seen
504 between the real-time PCR Cq values and the LAMP time of positivity values (Figure 5). Samples
505 from the asymptomatic grapevines (as assessed in 2016) consistently tested negative with both the
506 AY-SA-specific LAMP and the real-time PCR assays.

507 The specificities of the LAMP and real-time PCR assays developed were narrow and
508 limited only to AY-SA. In contrast, universal real-time PCR (Christensen et al., 2004) and nested
509 PCR (Van der Vyver et al. 2019) have broader specificities, and therefore discrepancies between
510 the tests can be expected. However, variations in the results between the universal real-time PCR
511 and the nested PCR can also be explained by differences in the specificities and concentrations of
512 the samples analyzed in the assays.

513

514 **Biological case study**

515 The presence of phytoplasma DNA in the collected grapevine field samples was initially analyzed
516 by AY-specific nested PCR (Van der Vyver et al. 2019), and within this study also with the
517 universal phytoplasma real-time PCR assay (Christensen et al. 2004), and the LAMP AY-SA_ftsH
518 assay and specific real-time PCR AY-SA_ftsH assay developed here (Table 3Table 4).

519 The symptomatology of the grapevines was not in complete agreement with the results of
520 the tests. Discordance was mainly observed in the pool of symptomatic grapevines, as two of 37

521 (5.4%) tested negative with the AY-SA-specific real-time PCR. No phytoplasma were detected in
522 any of the samples from the asymptomatic grapevines with either of these specific molecular tests.
523 However, five samples from the asymptomatic grapevines gave positive results only with the
524 universal phytoplasma real-time PCR assay. The majority of these samples (4/5; 80.0%) were
525 collected in November 2018. However, no other molecular tests detected target sequences in these
526 samples; therefore, these samples most likely contained other types of phytoplasmas, and not those
527 from the AY group, or they potentially contained a cross-reactive DNA sequence. Furthermore,
528 this indicates the possibility of mixed phytoplasma infections in these samples.

529 In the initial sampling in February 2016, all of the samples from the symptomatic
530 grapevines were positive in at least one of the assays tested. However, 35 grapevines (of 37;
531 94.6%) were positive in the AY-SA-specific molecular tests. The number of AY-SA-positive
532 grapevines was inconsistent, and decreased through the sampling period. Eleven samples from the
533 symptomatic grapevines were analyzed with all four phytoplasma assays at all four sampling
534 times. The number of positive samples here decreased from 11 to 5 from February to November
535 2016, and by the November 2018, only one sample was still positive. Furthermore, the
536 concentrations of the target phytoplasma DNA in the samples were quantified relatively by AY-
537 SA real-time PCR, through comparisons with the synthetic target dsDNA standard curves. Positive
538 grapevine samples contained from 4.3×10^4 up to 6.5×10^6 target molecules/ml; however, as the
539 samples needed to be diluted prior to the real-time PCR analysis, the lower target values fell below
540 the LOD of the assays.

541

542 **On-site sample adaptation of the LAMP assay**

543 A dipstick method and the direct use of a crude homogenate were evaluated for on-site sample
544 preparation, based on speed, simplicity, and performance. As grapevine material with detectable
545 concentrations of AY-SA was not available, the evaluation was performed on spiked extracts of
546 healthy grapevine leaf veins. The same manual plant tissue maceration step was used for both
547 methods, with different buffers used. Both of these methods were simple and relatively fast to
548 execute; however, each of the methods had its advantages and disadvantages.

549 The dipstick method was adaptable in terms of no pipetting was needed on-site, as the DNA
550 extraction step does not require pipetting (Supplementary figure S1). A wash step eliminated any
551 molecular test inhibitors, and hence there was no need to prepare sample dilutions. However,
552 although the dipsticks are cheap to prepare, they are not commercially available and have to be
553 prepared manually. The process is hard to standardize, as it requires hand cutting of the sticks.
554 Furthermore, the preparation of the sticks must be performed in a DNA-clean environment, to
555 avoid their contamination.

556 On the other hand, the direct use of the crude homogenate requires dilutions of the samples,
557 and therefore there is the need for pipetting. However, the process can be adapted to be more on-
558 site friendly by replacing the pipetting of the samples with a transfer with a single use inoculation
559 loop. However, imprecise preparation of the dilutions can result in inaccurate results and the
560 introduction of contamination.

561 The performance of each method was evaluated with the LAMP and real-time PCR assays.
562 The methods gave very similar results with the LAMP assay. The LOD was 10^5 target dsDNA
563 molecules/ml spiked grapevine extract for both methods, which indicated successful elution of the
564 DNA from the dipsticks into the LAMP reaction mix. Furthermore, the dipstick method was
565 successfully used also on a sample spiked with phytoplasma DNA. The crude homogenate method

566 gave good results also on the real-time PCR detection system; however, here the dipstick did not
567 provide satisfactory results. The elution of the samples from dipsticks appeared to be very
568 inefficient, as only two samples with 10^7 target dsDNA molecules/ml gave positive results. No
569 cross-reactivity or influence of the grapevine material was observed with any of the sample
570 preparation and detection system combinations.

571 The dipstick method was also suitable for short-term storage of the DNA for use in
572 molecular tests like LAMP. Synthetic DNA stored on washed and dried dipsticks was detected
573 after 3 weeks of storage if the initial sample concentration was 10^6 target dsDNA molecules/ml or
574 higher. However, as a LAMP detection system was used, the DNA loss on the dipstick could not
575 be assessed. The integrity of the DNA after storage is not known, although it was sufficient for
576 successful detection with the LAMP assay.

577

578 **Discussion**

579

580 Molecular detection of phytoplasmas is mostly focused on a limited number of target genes, as
581 targeting these regions is useful for phylogenetic and taxonomic studies (Bertaccini et al. 2019).
582 However, this can present a limitation for the design of tests for specific detection of a phytoplasma
583 group and/or with very specific requirements for the target sequence, such as with LAMP. On the
584 other hand, genomic data is becoming more available and can be tapped as a source of potential
585 novel target sequences for test design.

586 Here, we report on the identification of novel target sequences in the genomes of AY-SA
587 through analysis of the genomic sequences, followed by design of a specific LAMP assay and the
588 testing of its performance on a range of reference DNA samples and naturally contaminated

589 samples. We used the molecular tests developed for a case study of phytoplasma occurrence in an
590 experimental vineyard in the Vredendal region in South Africa, and adapted the LAMP assay for
591 on-site diagnostic use.

592 While relatively few genomes are available for the phytoplasmas associated with diseases
593 in plants, the amount of information is nevertheless too substantial to be analyzed manually.
594 Therefore, we adapted and applied an automated analysis approach based on comparisons of
595 genomic data (Thomsen et al. 2017). A custom assembled composite pipeline was used for the
596 design of the LAMP and real-time PCR assays, starting from whole genome information. The
597 programs and pipelines designed to implement genomic data for the development of molecular
598 assays are at present mainly adapted to the development of PCR assays (Pritchard et al. 2012;
599 Thomsen et al. 2017), and these cannot be easily transferred to the design of LAMP assays. The
600 present shortage of tools that would enable LAMP development from whole genome data puts the
601 method at a disadvantage in comparison to PCR and real-time PCR. Furthermore, some software
602 packages that were designed to identify signature candidates that are appropriate for LAMP assays
603 are no longer available, such as LAVA. At the time of the present study, there was no tool
604 available, to the best of our knowledge, for LAMP design from whole genome data that would
605 have suited our needs. On this note, a new Linux-based LAMP primer design tool was described
606 relatively recently (Jia et al. 2019), although this was not available at the initiation of our study.

607 The ability to rapidly and accurately identify plant pathogenic organisms represents a
608 critical aspect for the management of plant diseases. As well as the need to be rapid, an ideal
609 disease identification method should be simple and able to be performed on site. Among the
610 different molecular diagnostic approaches, LAMP technology can provide rapid and reliable

611 detection in resource-limited settings, and unlike PCR, LAMP can be transferred easily to an on-
612 site environment (Mori and Notomi 2020; Kogovšek et al. 2015).

613 Our pipeline identified DNA regions that enabled the development of specific LAMP and
614 real-time PCR assays. However, the wise selection of a negative dataset is crucial to the production
615 of target sequences of sufficient specificity (Thomsen et al. 2017). To ensure specificity of the
616 regions identified, a BLAST step was included, which compared the target regions against negative
617 samples that were not included in the training data. The modularity of the pipeline also allows the
618 user to adapt it to their needs. All of the tools included in the pipeline are also available as web
619 services with user-friendly graphic interfaces, and are therefore convenient for less proficient users
620 of bioinformatics tools. Quality control assessed with bioinformatics tools will not guarantee a
621 good and successful LAMP assay design. From 20 assays with similar quality parameters, only
622 four worked adequately under the required experimental conditions.

623 The LAMP assays with acceptable performance characteristics that were developed had
624 the same target region: the *ftsH* (syn. *hflB*) gene coding for ATP-dependent zinc-binding
625 membrane proteases FtsH/HflB. The *ftsH* genes are conserved and are usually present in multiple
626 copies in phytoplasma genomes. It was suggested that the abundance of *ftsH* genes in phytoplasma
627 genomes correspond with horizontal gene transfer, since they are often clustered within potential
628 mobile units (PMU) (Bai et al., 2006, Seemüller et al. 2011). Four *ftsH* genes were identified in
629 '*Catharanthus roseus*' AY strain De Villa chromosome (GenBank accession number, CP035949;
630 Coetzee et al. 2019), however none directly corresponded to PMU region as genome lack of any
631 identifiable PMU region (Huang et al., 2022). Some indications have linked the aggressiveness of
632 phytoplasmas and the structure of their FtsH proteins, making the *ftsH* gene an interesting target
633 for their detection (Seemüller et al. 2011, 2013).

634 The amplicon sequence of the developed LAMP AY-SA_ftsH assay corresponds to the
635 genomic sequence from 50691 bp to 50891 bp of the '*Catharanthus roseus*' AY strain De Villa
636 chromosome (GenBank accession number, CP035949; Coetzee et al. 2019). Only one target
637 sequence was identified in the draft AY-SA genome.

638 The sensitivity of the AY-SA-specific LAMP assay was comparable to that of real-time
639 PCR, with the LOD₉₅ for both assays in the range of $7-8 \times 10^3$ target dsDNA molecules/ml.
640 However, the sample volume in the LAMP assay was 2.5-fold that in the real-time PCR, per
641 reaction. This means that for successful detection at 95% confidence, the LAMP reaction should
642 contain at least 40 target copies, and the real-time PCR reaction at least 13 target copies. The
643 sensitivity did not significantly deviate from the theoretical LOD of real-time PCR. The LOD₉₅
644 for real-time PCR under error-free conditions is based on the calculation of three target copies per
645 reaction. However, the LOD of real samples is affected by noise caused by the sampling and
646 extraction, and the amplification reaction, and therefore the experimentally determined LOD can
647 be substantially higher (Forootan et al. 2017). The sensitivity of the LAMP reaction can also be
648 affected by the form of the target DNA. LAMP assays can be performed using non-denatured
649 template DNA (Nagamine et al. 2001); however, it was reported that an additional denaturation
650 step can increase the sensitivity of the LAMP reaction (Aryan et al. 2010). Indeed, heat
651 denaturation increased the sensitivity of the AY-SA LAMP assay for synthetic dsDNA (data not
652 shown).

653 Rapid development and deployment of molecular tests is essential to support new findings,
654 and for monitoring of novel pathogens and efficient diagnostics. Therefore, the appropriate
655 reference material is needed for test development and validation. Here, we have described the
656 combination of different reference materials and material sources that enable molecular test

657 development when reference and sample materials are scarce or difficult to obtain (Figure 1 **Error!**
658 **Reference source not found.**).

659 Both the AY-SA-specific LAMP and real-time PCR showed good performance criteria.
660 Some discordance between molecular tests and the symptomatology of the tested grapevines was
661 expected. The disease symptoms caused by phytoplasmas are similar to those of plant stress
662 (Bertaccini et al. 2014). Moreover, phytoplasmas are not distributed evenly within a plant, and can
663 appear to be present at low concentrations. Therefore, it is impossible to be certain that a negative
664 result means that the plant is actually phytoplasma free, or whether the result is effectively a false
665 negative (Christensen et al. 2004; Constable et al. 2003). For some host plants, it has been reported
666 that the degree of phytoplasma infection is correlated with the level of the visual symptoms
667 (Christensen et al. 2004). A similar correlation can be seen for AY-SA in grapevines, as the
668 sanitation status of the grapevines and the results of the AY-SA-specific real-time PCR here
669 corresponded at 94% (46/49 grapevines tested).

670 Furthermore, the comparison between the different universal and AY-SA-specific tests can
671 confirm the possibility of mixed infections with non-AY phytoplasmas (Botti and Bertaccini
672 2006). Infections with non-AY phytoplasmas have increased over the years, while infections with
673 AY-SA have decreased. This drop in phytoplasma infections is most likely connected to the
674 extreme drought that severely affected the Western Cape region in 2016 (Mahlalela et al. 2020).
675 Moreover, fewer grapevines were included in the further analysis in this study, and therefore some
676 positive samples might have been missed.

677 Concentration of target molecules in positive grapevine samples varied. Variability was
678 observed on the level of the plant and between plants. Variability in target concentrations between
679 plants was expected, since phytoplasma are known to be inconsistently distributed through the

680 plant (Christensen et al. 2004). Differences in seasonal distribution were clearly observed in 2016.
681 Concentration of the target in the test plants was typically higher in autumn, similarly as described
682 by Constable et al. (2003). In the following years, post extreme drought, (years 2017 and 2018)
683 the number of positive samples was too low to perform comparison between sampling seasons.

684 This newly developed LAMP assay is specific, and therefore it has the potential to address
685 key gaps in our knowledge of phytoplasmas through the extension of the study to vectors and other
686 host plants. The assays can be adopted in diagnostic laboratories and for epidemiological studies.
687 It is shown here to be very repeatable and reproducible, as consistent results were obtained
688 regardless of the instruments used, the experimental location, and the people who performed the
689 tests. The primary advantage of the LAMP method is its applicability to on-site settings. However,
690 it needs to be paired with a user-friendly on-site sample preparation method. Both of the methods
691 tested here, as the dipstick method and the direct use of crude homogenates, performed well in
692 combination with the LAMP assay. Moreover, the dipsticks provided an easy and adequate way
693 to store samples with high DNA concentrations at room temperature. Storing DNA on filter paper,
694 on chromatography paper, or on Flinders Technology Associates cards are known long-term
695 storage options (Thompson and Hrabak 2018; Owens and Szalanski 2005). However, none of these
696 systems provides fast and easy elution of the sample nucleic acids directly into the reaction mixture
697 of the detection assay. They require either direct addition to the reaction mixture of the paper with
698 the bound sample, or a separate nucleic acid elution step. Direct addition of the paper is not an
699 acceptable option for fluorometer detection systems like LAMP, as this disrupts the optical
700 detection. Therefore, the dipstick method would be especially convenient for sample transportation
701 if immediate freezing is not possible.

702 In this study, we have shown the easy and accessible design of molecular detection assays
703 based on LAMP and real-time PCR using whole genome data. While the LAMP assays require
704 experimental testing, the approach appears to be a viable way of increasing the pool of potential
705 target sequences of phytoplasmas. We have shown an efficient validation approach if reference
706 and sample materials are sparse. The molecular assays developed here are highly specific to AY-
707 SA, and show good sensitivity and reproducibility. The main advantage of this LAMP assay is its
708 applicability to the on-site diagnosis setting. This study is also the first to show the applicability
709 of the dipstick DNA isolation technique to a LAMP detection system, and its potential for DNA
710 storage.

711

712

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722

723 **Literature cited**

724

725 Altschul, S. F., Gish, W., Miller, W., Myers, E. W., and Lipman, D. J. 1990. Basic local alignment
726 search tool. *J. Mol. Biol.* 215:403-410.

727 Angelini, E., Luca Bianchi, G., Filippin, L., Morassutti, C., and Borgo, M. 2007. A new TaqMan
728 method for the identification of phytoplasmas associated with grapevine yellows by real-time
729 PCR assay. *J. Microbiol. Methods.* 68:613-622.

730 Aryan, E., Makvandi, M., Farajzadeh, A., Huygen, K., Bifani, P., Mousavi, S. L., et al. 2010. A
731 novel and more sensitive loop-mediated isothermal amplification assay targeting IS6110 for
732 detection of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* complex. *Microbiol. Res.* 165:211-220.

733 Bai, X., Zhang, J., Ewing, A., Miller, S. A., Jancso Radek, A., Shevchenko, D. V., et al. 2006.
734 Living with genome instability: the adaptation of phytoplasmas to diverse environments of
735 their insect and plant hosts. *J. Bacteriol.* 188(10): 3682-3696.

736 Bekele, B., Hodgetts, J., Tomlinson, J., Boonham, N., Nikolić, P., Swarbrick, P., et al. 2011. Use
737 of a real-time LAMP isothermal assay for detecting 16SrII and XII phytoplasmas in fruit and
738 weeds of the Ethiopian Rift Valley. *Plant Pathol.* 60:345-355.

739 Bertaccini, A., Duduk, B., Paltrinieri, S., and Contaldo, N. 2014. Phytoplasmas and phytoplasma
740 diseases: a severe threat to agriculture. *Am. J. Plant Sci.* 5:1763-1788.

741 Bertaccini, A., Fiore, N., Zamorano, A., Tiwari, A. K., and Rao, G. P. 2019. Molecular and
742 Serological Approaches in Detection of Phytoplasmas in Plants and Insects. In *Phytoplasmas:
743 Plant Pathogenic Bacteria - III*, Springer Singapore, pp. 105-136.

744 Botti, S., and Bertaccini, A. 2006. First report of phytoplasmas in grapevines in South Africa. *Plant
745 Dis.* 90:1360-1360.

- 746 Carstens, R., Petersen, Y., Stephan, D., and Burger, J. 2011. Current status of aster yellows disease
747 in infected vineyards in the Vredendal grape producing area of South Africa. *Phytopathogenic*
748 *Mollicutes*. 1:83-85.
- 749 Carstens, R. 2014. The incidence and distribution of grapevine yellows disease in South African
750 vineyards. Dissertation (MSc), Stellenbosch University. <http://hdl.handle.net/10019.1/86683>
- 751 Christensen, N. M., Nicolaisen, M., Hansen, M., and Schulz, A. 2004. Distribution of
752 phytoplasmas in infected plants as revealed by real-time PCR and bioimaging. *Mol. Plant-*
753 *Microbe Interact.* 17:1175-1184.
- 754 Coetzee, B., Douglas-Smit, N., Maree, H. J., Burger, J. T., Krüger, K., and Pietersen, G. 2019.
755 Draft genome sequence of a “*Candidatus Phytoplasma asteris*”-related strain (aster yellows,
756 subgroup 16SrI-B) from South Africa. *Microbiol. Resour. Announc.* 8:e00148-19.
- 757 Constable, F., and Bertaccini, A. 2017. Worldwide Distribution and Identification of Grapevine
758 Yellows Diseases. In: *Grapevine Yellows Diseases and Their Phytoplasma Agents*. Springer,
759 Cham. pp. 17-46.
- 760 Constable, F. E., Gibb, K. S., and Symons, R. H. 2003. Seasonal distribution of phytoplasmas in
761 Australian grapevines. *Plant Pathol.* 52:267-276.
- 762 Dermastia M, Bertaccini A, Constable F and Mehle N. 2017. Grapevine yellows diseases and their
763 phytoplasma agents - Biology and detection. eds. Springer International Publishing.
- 764 Dickinson, M. 2015. Loop-mediated isothermal amplification (LAMP) for detection of
765 phytoplasmas in the field. *Methods Mol. Biol.* 1302:98-111.
- 766 Engelbrecht, M., Joubert, J., and Burger, J. T. 2010. First report of aster yellows phytoplasma in
767 grapevines in South Africa. *Plant Dis.* 94:373.
- 768 EPPO 2018. PM 7/98 (3) Specific requirements for laboratories preparing accreditation for a plant

- 769 pest diagnostic activity. EPPO Bull. 48:387-404.
- 770 Forootan, A., Sjöback, R., Björkman, J., Sjögreen, B., Linz, L., and Kubista, M. 2017. Methods to
771 determine limit of detection and limit of quantification in quantitative real-time PCR (qPCR).
772 Biomol. Detect. Quantif. 12:1-6.
- 773 Hara-Kudo, Y., Nemoto, J., Ohtsuka, K., Segawa, Y., Takatori, K., Kojima, T., et al. 2007.
774 Sensitive and rapid detection of Vero toxin-producing *Escherichia coli* using loop-mediated
775 isothermal amplification. J. Med. Microbiol. 56:398-406.
- 776 Huang, C. T., Cho, S. T., Tan, C. M., Chiu, Y. C., Yang, J. Y., and Kuo, C. H. 2021. Comparative
777 Genome Analysis of ‘Candidatus Phytoplasma luffae’ Reveals the Influential Roles of
778 Potential Mobile Units in Phytoplasma Evolution. Front. Microbiol. Front. Microbiol.
779 13:773608.
- 780 Jia, B., Li, X., Liu, W., Lu, C., Lu, X., Ma, L., et al. 2019. GLAPD: Whole genome based LAMP
781 primer design for a set of target genomes. Front. Microbiol. 10:2860.
- 782 Kaneko, H., Kawana, T., Fukushima, E., and Suzutani, T. 2007. Tolerance of loop-mediated
783 isothermal amplification to a culture medium and biological substances. J. Biochem. Biophys.
784 Meth. 70:499-501.
- 785 Kogovšek, P., Hodgetts, J., Hall, J., Prezelj, N., Nikolić, P., Mehle, N., et al. 2015. LAMP assay
786 and rapid sample preparation method for on-site detection of flavescence dorée phytoplasma
787 in grapevine. Plant Pathol. 64:286-296.
- 788 Kogovšek, P., Mehle, N., Pugelj, A., Jakomin, T., Schroers, H. J., Ravnikar, M., et al. 2017. Rapid
789 loop-mediated isothermal amplification assays for grapevine yellows phytoplasmas on crude
790 leaf-vein homogenate has the same performance as qPCR. Eur. J. Plant Pathol. 148:75-84.
- 791 Kruger, K., Pietersen, G., Smit, N., and Carstens, R. 2015. Epidemiology of aster yellows

- 792 phytoplasma: alternate host plants and the vector *Mgenia fuscovaria* (Hemiptera:
793 Cicadellidae) in South Africa. In: Proceedings of the 18th Congress of the International
794 Council for the Study of Virus and Virus-like Diseases of Grapevine (ICVG), Ankara, Turkey.
795 pp. 126-127.
- 796 Kruger, K., Read, D., Stiller, M., and Pietersen, G. 2018. A potential new vector of aster yellows
797 phytoplasma in vineyards in South Africa. In: Proceedings of the 19th Congress of the
798 International Council for the Study of Virus and Virus-like Diseases of Grapevine (ICVG),
799 Santiago, Chile. pp. 88-89.
- 800 Mahlalela, P. T., Blamey, R. C., Hart, N. C. G., and Reason, C. J. C. 2020. Drought in the Eastern
801 Cape region of South Africa and trends in rainfall characteristics. *Clim. Dyn.* 55:2743-2759.
- 802 Mehle, N., Mermal, S., Vidmar, S., Viršček Marn, M., Dreo, T., Dermastia, M. 2018. First report
803 of carrot infection with phytoplasmas in Slovenia. In: proceedings of the 5th European Bois
804 Noir Workshop, Ljubljana, Slovenia. pp. 1-4.
- 805 Mori, Y., and Notomi, T. 2020. Loop-mediated isothermal amplification (LAMP): expansion of
806 its practical application as a tool to achieve universal health coverage. *J. Infect. Chemother.*
807 26:13-17.
- 808 Nagamine, K., Watanabe, K., Ohtsuka, K., Hase, T., and Notomi, T. 2001. Loop-mediated
809 isothermal amplification reaction using a nondenatured template. *Clin. Chem.* 47:1742-1743.
- 810 Nikolić, P., J., B., M., H., Ravnkar, M., and Dermastia, M. 2009. Development of diagnostic
811 method for Aster yellows phytoplasma detection on grapevine with real-time PCR. PIn:
812 *Zbornik predavanj in referatov 9. slovenskega posvetovanja o varstvu rastlin, Nova Gorica,*
813 *4.-5. marec 2009*, ed. Jože Maček. Ljubljana: Društvo za varstvo rastlin Slovenije. pp. 237-
814 241.

- 815 Notomi, T., Okayama, H., Masubuchi, H., Yonekawa, T., Watanabe, K., Amino, N., et al. 2000.
816 Loop-mediated isothermal amplification of DNA. *Nucleic Acids Res.* 28:e63.
- 817 Owens, C. B., and Szalanski, A. L. 2005. Filter paper for preservation, storage, and distribution of
818 insect and pathogen DNA samples. *J. Med. Entomol.* 42:709-711.
- 819 Paltrinieri, S., Contaldo, N., Nicolaisen, M., and Bertaccini, A. 2015. Phytoplasma strain
820 collections: the Q-bank database and the Q-collect project. *Phytopathogenic Mollicutes.*
821 5:S33.
- 822 Pirce, M., Ravnikar, M., Tomlinson, J., and Dreo, T. 2009. Improved fireblight diagnostics using
823 quantitative real-time PCR detection of *Erwinia amylovora* chromosomal DNA. *Plant Pathol.*
824 58:872-881.
- 825 Pritchard, L., Holden, N. J., Bielaszewska, M., Karch, H., and Toth, I. K. 2012. Alignment-free
826 design of highly discriminatory diagnostic primer sets for *Escherichia coli* O104:H4 outbreak
827 strains. *PLoS One.* (4):e34498.
- 828 R Core Team. 2020. R: A language and environment for statistical computing. R Foundation for
829 Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria.
- 830 Ritz, C., Baty, F., Streibig, J. C., and Gerhard, D. 2015. Dose-response analysis using R. *PLoS*
831 *One.* 10:e0146021.
- 832 Seemüller, E., Kampmann, M., Kiss, E., and Schneider, B. 2011. HflB gene-based
833 phytopathogenic classification of “Candidatus *Phytoplasma mali*” strains and evidence that
834 strain composition determines virulence in multiply infected apple trees. *Mol. Plant-Microbe*
835 *Interact.* 24:1258-1266.
- 836 Seemüller, E., Sule, S., Kube, M., Jelkmann, W., and Schneider, B. 2013. The AAA+ ATPases
837 and HflB/FtsH proteases of “Candidatus *Phytoplasma mali*”: phylogenetic diversity,

- 838 membrane topology, and relationship to strain virulence. *Mol. Plant-Microbe Interact.* 26:367-
839 376.
- 840 Thompson, M. M., and Hrabak, E. M. 2018. Capture and storage of plant genomic DNA on a
841 readily available cellulose matrix. *Biotechniques.* 65:285-287.
- 842 Thomsen, M. C. F., Hasman, H., Westh, H., Kaya, H., and Lund, O. 2017. RUCS: Rapid
843 identification of PCR primers for unique core sequences. *Bioinformatics.* 33:3917-3921.
- 844 Tomlinson, J. A., Boonham, N., and Dickinson, M. 2010. Development and evaluation of a 1-hour
845 DNA extraction and loop-mediated isothermal amplification assay for rapid detection of
846 phytoplasmas. *Plant Pathol.* 59:465-471.
- 847 Van der Vyver, A., Page, L., Maree, H., and Burger, J. 2019. Phytoplasma recovery phenotype - a
848 case study for aster yellows in South Africa. *Phytopathogenic Mollicutes.* 9:183.
- 849 Wang, D., Liu, F., Huo, G., Ren, D., and Li, Y. 2009. Development and evaluation of a loop-
850 mediated isothermal amplification method for detecting *Escherichia coli* O157 in raw milk.
851 *J. Rapid Methods Autom. Microbiol.* 17:55-66.
- 852 Zhang, X. H., Ye, Q., Liu, Y. D., Li, B., Ivanek, R., and He, K. W. 2013. Development of a LAMP
853 assay for rapid detection of different intimin variants of attaching and effacing microbial
854 pathogens. *J. Med. Microbiol.* 62:1665-1672.
- 855 Zou, Y., Mason, M. G., Wang, Y., Wee, E., Turni, C., Blackall, P. J., et al. 2017. Nucleic acid
856 purification from plants, animals and microbes in under 30 seconds. *PLoS Biol.* 15:e2003916.
857

858 **Table 1.** Testing of assay specificity against characterized phytoplasma isolates obtained from the
 859 International Phytoplasma Working Group and from carrot samples.

Sample	Host plant	Origin	Ribosomal group	Universal real-time PCR assay for phytoplasma ^a		AY-SA-specific real-time PCR ^b	
				Result	Cq	Result	Result ^d
D310/17 A	<i>Daucus carota</i> subsp. <i>sativus</i>	Slovenia	16SrI	Pos	18.3	Neg ^f	Neg ^g
D310/17 B	<i>Daucus carota</i> subsp. <i>sativus</i>	Slovenia	16SrI	Pos	22.1	Neg ^f	Neg ^g
D322/17 A	<i>Daucus carota</i> subsp. <i>sativus</i>	Slovenia	16SrI	Pos	16.5	Neg ^f	Neg ^g
D322/17 B	<i>Daucus carota</i> subsp. <i>sativus</i>	Slovenia	16SrI	Pos	20.7	Neg ^f	Neg ^g
D357/17 A	<i>Daucus carota</i> subsp. <i>sativus</i>	Slovenia	16SrI	Pos	15.5	Neg ^f	Neg ^g
D357/17 B	<i>Daucus carota</i> subsp. <i>sativus</i>	Slovenia	16SrI	Pos	21.3	Neg ^f	Neg ^g
NJ-AY ^e	Aster	USA	16SrI-A	Pos	19.9	Neg ^f	Neg ^g
AY2192 ^e	NA	NA	16SrI-B	Pos	19.0	Neg ^f	Neg ^g
NA ^e	Periwinkle	Italy	16SrI-B	Pos	19.6	Neg ^f	Neg ^g
PRIVA ^e	Primula	Germany	16SrI-B	Pos	19.4	Neg ^f	Neg ^g
RV ^e	Brassicaceae	France	16SrI-B	Pos	15.7	Neg ^f	Neg ^g
SIL ^e	<i>Silene vulgaris</i>	Italy	16SrI-B	Pos	17.9	Neg ^f	Neg ^g
CVT ^e	Periwinkle	Thiland	16SrI-B	Pos	15.6	Neg ^f	Neg ^g
DIV ^e	<i>Diplotaxis eruroides</i>	Spain	16SrI-B	Pos	14.8	Neg ^f	Neg ^g
C-CP ^e	Trifolium	Canada	16SrI-C	Pos	15.7	Neg ^f	Neg ^g
ACLR ^e	NA	NA	16SrI-F	Pos	14.2	Neg ^f	Neg ^g
FBPSA ^e	<i>Crotalaria saltiana</i>	Sudan	16SrII-C	Pos	16.3	Neg ^f	Neg ^g
CX ^e	<i>Prunus</i>	Canada	16SrIII-A	Pos	15.7	Neg ^f	Neg ^g
KVI ^e	Trifolium	Italy	16SrIII-B	Pos	13.4	Neg ^f	Neg ^g
GYU ^e	<i>Vitis vinifera</i>	Italy	16SrIII-B	Pos	18.5	Neg ^f	Neg ^g
ASHY ^e	NA	NA	16SrVII-A	Pos	14.1	Neg ^f	Neg ^g
PEY ^e	<i>Pichris echioides</i>	Italy	16SrIX-C	Pos	19.0	Neg ^f	Neg ^g
AP-15 ^e	Malus	Italy	16SrX-A	Pos	16.1	Neg ^f	Neg ^g
ASLO ^e	Aster	Slovenia	16SrXII-A	Pos	14.7	Neg ^f	Neg ^g
CH1 ^e	<i>Vitis vinifera</i>	Italy	16SrXII-A	Pos	16.4	Neg ^f	Neg ^g

STOL ^e	Capsicum	Serbia	16SrXII-A	Pos	15.2	Neg ^f	Neg ^g
MOL ^e	<i>Prunus</i>	France	16SrXII-A	Pos	13.4	Neg ^f	Neg ^g

860 NA, not available; Pos, positive; Neg, negative

861 ^aChristensen *et al.* (2004)

862 ^breal-time PCR AY-SA_ftsH assay

863 ^cLAMP AY-SA_ftsH assay

864 ^dResult for 10× dilution of the original sample

865 ^eSamples from the International Phytoplasma Working Group collection

866 ^fNegative real-time PCR reaction after 45 cycles

867 ^gNegative LAMP reaction after 30 min

868

869 **Table 2.** Primers and probes for the molecular tests designed and used in this study.

Molecular assay	Target gene	Primer/ probe	Sequence (5'-3')
Real-time PCR	<i>ftsH</i>	AY-SA_ftsH_R	CCCAAAAGGTGCAAAAAATAACTA
		AY-SA_ftsH_P ^a	FAM-CGTGTGGGAATTCGGGCGGTTATAA-BHQ
		AY-SA_ftsH_R	AAAGAAAGTTTCTGTTTCTGGTGTC
LAMP	<i>ftsH</i>	AY-SA_ftsH_F3	TGAAGCAGGACACGCTAT
		AY-SA_ftsH_B3	CAAAAATTAATTCTTCAGCCACA
		AY-	CCGAATTCCCACACGGAATAATTAAGTTGGAAC
		SA_ftsH_FIP ^a	ATGCCCA
		AY-	AATGACACCAGAAACAGAACTTTCCGTCCCC
		SA_ftsH_BIP ^a	TAAATAAGATGT

870 ^aHPLC purified

871

872

873 **Table 3.** Results of the molecular tests of the grapevine samples collected in February 2016. The
 874 symptomatic and asymptomatic grapevines were defined in February and November 2016 based
 875 on their apparent symptomatology. Asymptomatic grapevine samples were analyzed as undiluted
 876 DNA extracts. Symptomatic grapevine samples were analyzed as undiluted DNA extracts in nested
 877 PCR and as 10-fold dilutions in real-time PCR assays. For the LAMP assays, symptomatic
 878 grapevine samples were predominantly analyzed as undiluted DNA, although some samples
 879 needed to be 10-fold diluted due to shortage of the DNA extract (as indicated).

880

Sample	February 2016				November 2016			
	Real-time PCR ^a	LAMP ^a	Universal phytoplasma real-time PCR	AY nested PCR	Real-time PCR ^a	LAMP ^a	Universal phytoplasma real-time PCR	AY nested PCR
Asymptomatic grapevines								
A01	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg
A12	Neg	Neg	Pos	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg
A13	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg
A19	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg
A02	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg
A25	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg
A26	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg
A29	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg
A03	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg
A05	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg
A07	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg
A08	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg
Symptomatic grapevines								
S14	Neg	Neg ^c	Neg	Pos	/	/	/	Neg
S15	Pos	Pos	Pos	Pos	/	/	/	Neg
S17	Pos	Pos ^c	Pos	Pos	/	/	/	Neg
S18	Pos	Pos ^c	Pos	Pos	Neg	Neg ^c	Neg	Neg

S19	Pos	Pos ^c	Pos	Pos	/	/	/	Neg
S23	Pos	Pos	Pos	Pos	/	/	/	Neg
S24	Pos	Pos	Pos	Pos	/	/	/	Neg
S26	Neg	Neg ^c	Pos	Pos	/	/	/	Neg
S29	Disc	Pos	Pos	Pos	/	/	/	Neg
S31	Pos	Neg	Pos	Pos	/	/	/	Neg
S32	Pos	Pos	Pos	Pos	/	/	/	Neg
S33	Pos	Pos	Pos	Pos	/	/	/	Neg
S34	Pos	Pos ^c	Pos	Pos	/	/	/	NA
S35	Pos	Pos ^c	Pos	Pos	/	/	/	Neg
S39	Pos	Neg ^c	Pos	Pos	Pos	Pos	Pos	Pos
S04	Pos	Neg	Pos	Pos	/	/	/	Neg
S40	Pos	Pos ^c	Pos	Pos	Pos	Pos ^c	Pos	Pos
S43	Pos	Pos	Pos	Pos	/	/	/	Neg
S44	Pos	Neg ^c	Pos	Pos	Neg	Neg ^c	Neg	Neg
S46	Pos	Pos ^c	Pos	Pos	Pos	Pos	Pos	Pos
S47	Pos	Neg ^c	Pos	Pos	/	/	/	Neg
S48	Pos	Pos	Pos	Pos	Neg	Neg	Neg	Pos
S49	Pos	Pos ^c	Pos	Pos	/	/	/	Neg
S05	Pos	Neg ^c	Pos	Pos	/	/	/	Neg
S51	Pos	Pos	Pos	Pos	Pos	Pos	Pos	Pos
S52	Pos	Pos ^c	Pos	Pos	Neg	Neg ^c	Neg	Neg
S54	Pos	Pos ^c	Pos	Pos	Pos	Pos ^c	Pos	Pos
S55	Pos	Pos	Pos	Pos	Neg	Neg ^c	Neg	Neg
S56	Pos	Neg ^c	Pos	Pos	/	/	/	Neg
S57	Pos	Neg ^c	Pos	Pos	/	/	/	Neg
S58	Pos	Pos	Pos	Pos	Neg	Neg ^c	Neg	Neg
S59	Pos	Pos	Pos	Pos	/	/	/	Neg
S06	Pos	Pos	Pos	Pos	/	/	/	Neg
S60	Pos	Pos	Pos	Pos	/	/	/	Neg
S07	Pos	Pos	Pos	Pos	/	/	/	Neg
S08	Pos	Pos	Pos	Pos	/	/	/	Neg
S09	Pos	Pos ^c	Pos	Pos	/	/	/	Neg

882 ^a real-time PCR AY-SA_ftsH assay

883 ^b LAMP AY-SA_ftsH assay

884 ^c samples 10-fold diluted

885 **Table 4.** Results of the molecular tests of the grapevine samples collected in February 2017 and
 886 November 2018. The symptomatic and asymptomatic grapevines were defined in February 2016
 887 based on their apparent symptomatology. Asymptomatic grapevine samples were analyzed as
 888 undiluted DNA extracts. Symptomatic grapevine samples were analyzed as undiluted DNA
 889 extracts in nested PCR and as 10-fold dilutions in real-time PCR assays. For the LAMP assays,
 890 symptomatic grapevine samples were predominantly analyzed as undiluted DNA, although some
 891 samples needed to be 10-fold diluted due to shortage of the DNA extract (as indicated).

Sample	February 2017				November 2018			
	Real-time PCR ^a	LAMP ^a	Universal phytoplasma real-time PCR	AY nested PCR	Real-time PCR ^a	LAMP ^a	Universal phytoplasma real-time PCR	AY nested PCR
Asymptomatic grapevines								
A01	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	/	/	Neg
A12	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Pos	Neg
A13	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	/	/	/	Neg
A19	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg
A02	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Pos	Neg
A25	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Pos	Neg
A26	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg
A29	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg
A03	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Pos	Neg
A05	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	/	/	/	Neg
A07	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	/	/	/	Neg
A08	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Disc.	Neg	Neg	Neg
Symptomatic grapevines								
S14	/	/	/	Neg	/	/	/	Neg
S15	/	/	/	Neg	/	/	/	Neg
S17	/	/	/	Neg	/	/	/	Pos
S18	Pos	Pos ^c	Pos	Pos	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg
S19	/	/	/	Neg	/	/	/	Neg
S23	/	/	/	Neg	/	/	/	Neg

S24	/	/	/	Neg	/	/	/	Neg
S26	/	/	/	Neg	/	/	/	Neg
S29	/	/	/	Neg	/	/	/	Neg
S31	/	/	/	Neg	/	/	/	Neg
S32	/	/	/	Neg	/	/	/	Neg
S33	/	/	/	Neg	/	/	/	NA
S34	/	/	/	NA	/	/	/	NA
S35	/	/	/	Neg	/	/	/	Neg
S39	Neg	Neg ^c	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg
S04	/	/	/	Neg	/	/	/	Pos
S40	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg ^c	Neg	Pos
S43	/	/	/	Neg	/	/	/	Neg
S44	Pos	Pos	Pos	Pos	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg
S46	Neg	Neg ^c	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Pos	Pos
S47	/	/	/	Neg	/	/	/	Neg
S48	Neg	Neg ^c	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Pos
S49	/	/	/	Neg	/	/	/	NA
S05	Neg	Neg ^c	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg
S51	Pos	Pos	Pos	Pos	Pos	Pos	Pos	Neg
S52	Neg	Neg ^c	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg
S54	Neg	Neg ^c	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Pos	Neg
S55	/	/	/	Neg	/	/	/	Neg
S56	/	/	/	Neg	/	/	/	Neg
S57	/	/	/	Neg	/	/	/	Neg
S58	Neg	Neg ^c	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg
S59	/	/	/	Neg	/	/	/	Neg
S06	/	/	/	Neg	/	/	/	Pos
S60	/	/	/	Neg	/	/	/	Neg
S07	/	/	/	Neg	/	/	/	Neg
S08	/	/	/	Neg	/	/	/	Neg
S09	/	/	/	Neg	/	/	/	Neg

892 ^a real-time PCR AY-SA_ftsH assay

893 ^b LAMP AY-SA_ftsH assay

894 ^c samples 10-fold diluted

895 Pos, positive; Neg, negative; Disc, discordant or inconclusive; NA, not available (lack of sample
896 material); / samples not analyzed with all of the methods due to lack of sample material
897

898 **Table 5.** Comparison of performance parameters determined for individual tests according to
 899 sanitary status of the grapevines in February 2016, and according to the universal phytoplasma
 900 real-time PCR assay (Christensen et al. 2004) and AY nested PCR (Van der Vyver et al. 2019).

Performance parameter	According to sanitary status				According to universal phytoplasma real-time PCR assay		
	AY-SA real-time PCR	AY-SA LAMP	Universal phytoplasma real-time PCR	AY nested PCR	AY-SA real-time PCR	AY-SA LAMP	AY nested PCR
Total analyzed samples	48	49	49	49	113	114	114
Prevalence	0.75	0.76	0.76	0.76	0.45	0.46	0.46
Sensitivity	0.94	0.73	0.97	1.00	0.84	0.69	0.87
Specificity	1.00	1.00	0.92	1.00	0.98	1.00	0.94
False positive rate	0.00	0.00	0.08	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.06
False negative rate	0.06	0.27	0.03	0.00	0.16	0.31	0.13
Positive predictive value	1.00	1.00	0.92	1.00	0.98	1.00	0.92
Negative predictive value	0.86	0.55	0.03	1.00	0.88	0.79	0.89
Positive likelihood ratio	NA	NA	11.68	NA	52.28	NA	13.41
Negative likelihood ratio	0.06	0.27	0.03	0.00	0.16	0.31	0.14
Accuracy	0.96	0.80	0.96	1.00	0.92	0.86	0.90
Diagnostic odds ratio	NA	NA	396.00	NA	327.88	NA	93.21

901 NA, not applicable.

902

903 **Figure captions**

904 **Figure 1.** Overview of the LAMP assay development process and the parameters defined for each
905 step. The process is divided into six steps: 1. Rapid identification of PCR primers for unique core
906 sequences (i.e., RUCS); 2. Specificity confirmation using blastn; 3. Design of LAMP primers
907 using Primer Explorer v5; 4. Selection of appropriate LAMP assays based on the minimum
908 selection criteria; 5. Identification of the LAMP amplicon genetic position.

909 ^aGenome of grapevine yellows phytoplasmas from South Africa.

910 ^bComplying with defined minimum criteria for choosing LAMP assays

911

912 **Figure 2.** Development and validation steps and types of reference material used for the LAMP
913 and real-time PCR assays.

914

915 **Figure 3.** Schematic overview of the complete LAMP design process. Green, exploration of the
916 genome databases and selection of the genomic data implemented in the analysis; blue,
917 computation, including *in-silico* quality control; yellow, experimental part of the design process.

918

919 **Figure 4.** Correlation between time of positivity (T_p) and corresponding T_m of the LAMP AY-
920 SA_ftsH assay amplification product. Samples with lower T_p produced amplification products
921 with higher T_m , and *vice versa*. T_m of the amplification products ranged from 82.1 °C to 83.1 °C.

922

923 **Figure 5.** Correlation between average real-time PCR AY-SA_ftsH assay's C_q and LAMP AY-
924 SA_ftsH assay's time of positivity for positive grapevine samples (10-fold dilutions tested in both
925 assays).

926

1. RUCS	
Entry point	Find unique core sequences
Positive genomes	AY_Mgenia ^a AY_Periwinkle ^a
Reference	AY_Periwinkle ^a
Negative genomes	73 phytoplasma and mycoplasma genomes (Annex A)
K-mer size	20 bp
Read length	250 bp
Unique core sequences	802
Unique core sequences (>200 bp)	11
2. Blastn	
Parameters	Default
Database	nr/nt
Input sequences	11 unique core sequences (>200 bp)
3. Primer Explorer v5	
Parameter set	Automatic judgment
Detail settings:	
Parameter condition	AT rich
Length F2/B2	15-25 bp
Length F3/B3	15-25 bp
GC rate	25-65
Results:	
Seq1	258 assays
Seq2	0 assays
Seq3	54 assays
Seq4	0 assays
Seq5	0 assays
Seq6	0 assays
Seq7	0 assays
Seq8	0 assays
Seq9	0 assays
Seq10	0 assays
Seq11	774 assays
4. Parameter-based selection^b	
Seq1	8 assays
Seq3	5 assays
Seq11	7 assays

Figure 1. Overview of the LAMP assay development process and the parameters defined for each step. The process is divided into six steps: 1. Rapid identification of PCR primers for unique core sequences (i.e., RUCS); 2. Specificity confirmation using blastn; 3. Design of LAMP primers using Primer Explorer v5; 4. Selection of appropriate LAMP assays based on the minimum selection criteria; 5. Identification of the LAMP amplicon genetic position.

^aGenome of grapevine yellows phytoplasmas from South Africa.
^bComplying with defined minimum criteria for choosing LAMP assays

100x165mm (150 x 150 DPI)

Figure 2. Development and validation steps and types of reference material used for the LAMP and real-time PCR assays.

390x204mm (150 x 150 DPI)

Figure 3. Schematic overview of the complete LAMP design process. Green, exploration of the genome databases and selection of the genomic data implemented in the analysis; blue, computation, including in-silico quality control; yellow, experimental part of the design process.

85x120mm (150 x 150 DPI)

Figure 4. Correlation between time of positivity (Tp) and corresponding Tm of the LAMP AY-SA_ftsH assay amplification product. Samples with lower Tp produced amplification products with higher Tm, and vice versa. Tm of the amplification products ranged from 82.1 °C to 83.1 °C.

132x60mm (96 x 96 DPI)

Figure 5. Correlation between average real-time PCR AY-SA_ftsH assay's Cq and LAMP AY-SA_ftsH assay's time of positivity for positive grapevine samples (10-fold dilutions tested in both assays).

132x66mm (96 x 96 DPI)

Alič *et al.*Genome-informed design of a LAMP assay for the specific detection of the strain of '*Candidatus* Phytoplasma P. asteris' phytoplasma occurring in grapevines in South Africa**Table S1** List of genomes used as a negative data set input for pipeline analysis for the identification of the specific sequences using RUCS software. The list contains 73 complete or draft genomes of phytoplasma (18 genomes) and mycoplasma (55 genomes) derived from NCBI/Genbank database.

Name	NCBI/GenBank accession number
New Jersey aster yellows phytoplasma strain NJAY	MAPF01000000
Aster yellows witches'-broom phytoplasma AYWB	CP000061.1
Strawberry lethal yellows phytoplasma (CPA) strain NZSb11	NC_021236.1
Vaccinium witches' broom phytoplasma strain VAC	AKIN01000000
Wheat blue dwarf phytoplasma	AVAO01000000
Echinacea purpurea' witches' broom phytoplasma strain NCHU2014	LKAC01000000
' <i>Candidatus</i> Phytoplasma aurantifolia' strain WBDL	MWKN01000000
' <i>Candidatus</i> Phytoplasma australiense'	NC_010544.1
' <i>Candidatus</i> Phytoplasma mali' strain AT	CU469464.1
"Stolbur" phytoplasma	FO393428.1
"Stolbur' phytoplasma strain 284/09	FO393427.1
Rice orange leaf phytoplasma strain LD1	MIEP01000000
Poinsettia branch-inducing phytoplasma strain JR1	AKIK01000000
Phytoplasma sp. strain Vc33 3J-1	LLKK01000000
Onion yellows phytoplasma strain OY-M	NC_005303.2
Milkweed yellows phytoplasma strain MW1	AKIL01000000
Maize bushy stunt phytoplasma strain M3	CP015149.1
Italian clover phyllody phytoplasma str. MA1	AKIM01000000
Mycoplasma ovipneumoniae NM2010	JAKV01000000
Mycoplasma orale ATCC 23714	ATUH01000000

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Name	NCBI/GenBank accession number
Mycoplasma opalescens ATCC 27921	JOOB01000000
Mycoplasma molare ATCC 27746	JHWG01000000
Mycoplasma mobile 163K	NC_006908.1
Mycoplasma meleagridis ATCC 25294	JZXN01000000
Mycoplasma lipofaciens ATCC 35015	JMKY01000000
Mycoplasma leonicaptivi ATCC 49890	JHWE01000000
Mycoplasma leachii 06049	LAUU01000000
Mycoplasma iowae 695	AGFP01000000
Mycoplasma iners ATCC 19705	JNJW01000000
Mycoplasma imitans ATCC 51306	JADI01000000
Mycoplasma hyosynoviae isolate NPL7	JFKG01000000
Mycoplasma hyorhina SK76	NC_019552.1
Mycoplasma hyopneumoniae isolate J	NC_007295.1
Mycoplasma hominis ATCC 23114	NC_013511.1
Mycoplasma haemocanis isolate Illinois	NC_016638.1
Mycoplasma glycohilum ATCC 35277	JHYE01000000
Mycoplasma genitalium G37	NC_000908.2
Mycoplasma gallisepticum isolate R	AE015450.2
Mycoplasma gallinarum DSM 19816	JHZE01000000
Mycoplasma gallinaceum isolate B2096	CP011021.1
Mycoplasma flocculare ATCC 27399	NZ_CP007585.1
Mycoplasma fermentans M64	NC_014921.1
Mycoplasma feriruminatoris isolate G5847	ANFU01000000

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Name	NCBI/GenBank accession number
Mycoplasma felis ATCC 23391	JNKA01000000
Mycoplasma felifaucium ATCC 43428	JHXS01000000
Mycoplasma elephantis ATCC 51980	JHXU01000000
Mycoplasma cynos C142	NC_019949.1
Mycoplasma crocodyli MP145	NC_014014.1
Mycoplasma cricetuli ATCC 35279	JAHB01000000
Mycoplasma conjunctivae HRC/581T	NC_012806.1
Mycoplasma columborale ATCC 29258	JNJZ01000000
Mycoplasma columbinum ATCC 29257	JONY01000000
Mycoplasma collis ATCC 35278	JNJY01000000
Mycoplasma cloacale ATCC 35276	JNJL01000000
Mycoplasma capricolum subsp. capricolum ATCC 27343	NC_007633.1
Mycoplasma canis PG 14	NZ_CP014281.1
Mycoplasma canadense	NZ_AP014631.1
Mycoplasma californicum isolate ST-6	NZ_CP007521.1
Mycoplasma buteonis isolate ATCC 51371	JPOK01000000
Mycoplasma bovoculi M165/69	NZ_CP007154.1
Mycoplasma bovis PG45	NC_014760.1
Mycoplasma bovirhinis isolate GS01	NZ_CP024049.1
Mycoplasma bovigenitalium 51080	AORH01000000
Mycoplasma auris 15026	AORI01000000
Mycoplasma arthritidis 158L3-1	NC_011025.1
Mycoplasma arginini	NZ_AP014657.1

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Name	NCBI/GenBank accession number
Mycoplasma anseris ATCC 49234	JNJX01000000
Mycoplasma anatis 1340	AFVJ01000000
Mycoplasma alvi ATCC 29626	JNJU01000000
Mycoplasma alligatoris A21JP2	ADNC01000000
Mycoplasma alkalescens 14918	AMWK01000000
Mycoplasma agassizii isolate ATCC 700616	FWXE01000000
Mycoplasma agalactiae PG2	NC_009497.1

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Table S1. Nucleotide sequences of the target dsDNA (gBlock sequences) used for experimental evaluation of LAMP assays

Target dsDNA name	Length	Sequence
target gBlock_Seq1	557	TGCATGATCTACGTGCGTCACATGCAGTACATGAAAAAACTAAATTTAGATTAATACTAAAAGATATCTTTTTAACCTATTCCA AATGTCCTTTAGGTAAGATAAAAATTCATAATCATATTAAGAATTAATGGCTTCTAAAAACAAGAAATATCATATATCATT CTAATACCGAAAACCATCAAGACCATAAAGAAATCCATACTCATGTTTGTTCATTAACAAAACGTATCAAATTACAAATC AAAGATTCTTTGACATCGAAGGTTTTTCATCCAAAATGAATCTGCCCGTGATATCGAAAAATCAATTAATACTATATCAAAAAAG ATGGTGACTTCATCGAAGAAGGTACTCCAAGACATAAAAAATACGTTTCGTCAAAAACCAAAAAGAAGACGTAAAAAATTAATC TATGATGAAATTGATAGATTAAGAACAATATTATTATGATGATAATTTAACTTTAACTCAAGTTAAAAAATCTCTTGATACTT TCATTAAGATCTTGATCGTGACACTAGCTCAGATTCAGTAGACCGCTGTTG
target gBlock_Seq3	560	TGCATGATCTACGTGCGTCACATGCAGTACTTTTTATTATGAACAAATAGATTTAATTGAAAAAATCCTAAAAAAGTTTCAT CAAACAATCAGAAGATTGCTTGAAGAACTTGA AACGAACTGAATCATTTTTTAGTTTTGATACTTTAAAGATAACGACAC TACCCAAGAAATTAATAATGGCTATAAAGGAAGAGATGATTTCTGAGCATCGTCTAAATCCATTGTAATCGAGGGTGCTAGTAA ACTTGGTAAAACCGAGTTATAATTAGTTATCTAAATAATCAACGAGTACAATTAATTATATCAGGGGCTCGTTAGATTTAAC AAAAATAGCTATAATGATAGGTTTAAAAATCGATGTTTATGATGATAAAGTATAACTGATATTAGACGTGCTGGTTATTTAAA AACATTATTGGAGGCCAAAGAGGATTTATAGTTGATGTTAAATATTCTCCAAAAGAAAATTAATCTGGTAATAAATTATCTATCT TTTTATGTAATGAAGATATTAGTTCACTAGCTCAGATTCAGTAGACCGCTGTTG
target gBlock_Seq11	560	TGCATGATCTACGTGCGTCACATGCAGTACTTAGTTGTAAGAAATCAAAAAAGAAATTAATACTAAACAAGAATTAGAAGAAGC AATCGACCGTGTGTTGATGGGTCTGCCAAAAATCAATTAATACAACGAAGAAGAACGAAAAATGGTAGCTTATCATGAAG CAGGACACGCTATTATAGGAATTAAGTTGGAACATGCCAAAAAGGTGCAAAAAATAACTATTATCCGTGTGGGAATTCGGG CGTTATAATTAATGACACCAGAAACAGAAAATTTCTTTTCATCTAAAAACGTATGCTTACCCAAATTACATCTTATTAGGG GGACGTGTGGCTGAAGAATTAATTTTGGATGATGTTTCTTCTGTTGCTTATGATGATTTTAAACAAGCCACTAAAAATAGCTCGCT TAATGGTTACTAAAACGGCATGAGCGACCTTGGAGTAAGCCAAGATTCAGAGTTTTCTGATAAAAACATTAATTGATCAAGAAA TTAAAAAATAATTGATAATTGTTATTCAGCTCAGATTCAGTAGACCGCTGTTG
target gBlock_Seq1-3-11	1557	TGCATGATCGTGCGTCACATGCAGTACATGAAAAAACTAAATTTAGATTAATACTAAAGATATCTTTTTAACCTATTCCAAT GTCCTTTAGGTAAGATAAAAATTCATAATCATATTAAGAATTAATGGCTTCTAAAAACAAGAAATATCATATATCATTCTA ATACCGAAAACCATCAAGACCATAAAGAAATCCATACTCATGTTTGTTCATTAACAACAACGTTATCAAATTACAAAATCAA GATTTCTTTGACATCGAAGGTTTTTCATCCAAAATGAATCTGCCCGTGATATCGAAAAATCAATTAATACTATCAAAAAAGATG GTGACTTCATCGAAGAAGGTACTCCAAGACATAAAAAATACGTTTCGTCAAAAACCAAAAAGAAGAACGTAAACAATTAATCTAT GATGAAATTGATAGATTAAGAACAATATTATTATGATGATAATTTAACTTTAACTCAAGTTAAAAAATCTCTTGATACTTTCA TTAAAGATCTTGATCGTGATTTTTATTATGAACAAATAGATTTAATTGAAAAAATCCTAAAAAAGTTTCATCAACAATCAG AAGATTTGCTTGAAGAACTTGA AACGAACTGAATCATTTTTTAGTTTTGATACTTTTAAAGATAACGACACTACCCAAGAAA TTAAATGGCTATAAAGGAAGAGATGATTTCTGAGCATCGTCTAAATCCATTGTAATCGAGGGTGCTAGTAAACTTGGTAAAA CCGAGTTTATAATTAGTTATCTAAATAATCAACGAGTACAATTAATTATATCAGGGGCTCGTTAGATTTTAAACAATAAGCTA TAATGATAGGTTTAAAAATCGATGTTTATGATGATAAAGTATAACTGATATTAGACGTGCTGGTTTATTTAAAAACATTTGGG GGCAAAGAGGATTTATAGTTGATGTTAAATATTCTCCAAAAGAAAATTAATCTGGTAATAAATTATCTATCTTTTATGTAATG AAGATATTAGTTTTAGTTGTAAGAAATCAAAAAGAATTAATACTAAACAAGAATTAGAAGAAGCAATCGACCGTGTGTTTGTG GGTCTGCCAAAAATCAATTAATAACAACGAAGAAGAACGAAAAATGGTAGCTTATCATGAAGCAGGACACGCTATTATAGG AATTAAGTTGGAATGCCCCAAAAGGTGCAAAAAATAACTATTATTCCGTGTGGGAATTCGGGCGGTTATAATTTAATGACAC CAGAAACAGAACTTTCTTTTCATCTAAAAACGTATGCTTACCAAAATACATCTTATTAGGGGACGTGGCTGAGTAAAGAA TAATTTTTGATGATGTTTCTTCTGGTGCTTATGATGATTTTAAACAAGCCACTAAAAATAGCTCGCTTAATGGTTACTAAAACGG CATGAGCGACCTTGGAGTAAGCCAAGATTCAGAGTTTTCTGATAAAAACATTAATTGATCAAGAAATTAAAAAAATAATTGATA TTGTTATTCAGCTCAGATTCAGTAGACCGCTGTTG

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Table S1. Nucleotide sequences specific to AY-SA genomes and selected for LAMP primer design based on predefined criteria.

Sequence code name	Sequence length	Average GC %	Sequence
Seq1	651	25.4	AAAGATAAATAAAAAAATAGCCCCTAATCTAATAGGGGCTTTAACAAGAAAGAGATAAAAAATGAAAAAACTAAAT TTAGATTAATACTAAAGATATCTTTTAAACCTATTCCAAATGTCCTTTAGGTAAAAGATAAAAAATCATAATCATATTA GAATTAATGGCTTCTAAAAACAAGAAATATCATATATCATTCTAATACCGAAAACCATCAAGACCATAAAGAAATC CATACTCATGTTTGTTCATTAACAAAAACGTTATCAAATTACAAATCAAAGATTCTTTGACATCGAAGGTTTCATCC CAAAATGAATCTGCCCGTGATATCGAAAAATCAATTAACCTATATCAAAAAAGATGGTGACTTCATCGAAGAAGGTAC TCCAAGACATAAAAAATACGTTCGTCAAAACCAAAAAAGAAGAACGTAACAATTAATCTATGATGAAATGATAGATT AAAAGAACAATATTATGATGATAATTTAACTTTAACTCAAGTTAAAAAATCTCTTGATACTTTCATTAAGATCTTG ATCGTGATTTTATTATGAACAAATAGATTTAATTGAAAAATCCTAAAAAAAAGTTCATCAACAATCAGAAGATTT GCTTGAAGAACCTGAAAAACGA
Seq2	501	21.6	GTTGAACTAATAACCAACAAGAACAAGAAATATATAATGCTATTCTTAGAAAAATAGAATCTGAAGTTGATGAATTA ACAAATATTAAGAAATAGTTTATCGTCCAGATGGTAAAACCTATAAAGCATATTAATAATAGATTCTCAAACAAAA AAGAAATTAAGAATTTTATCATGATGATGGTAAAACCTATACTTTGGATTAAGAATTTGATCCTCAAACCTAGTTT GCAAAATAAAAAATACTATTACATAATGAACAAGGAAAAAATTATACAAATTATTAACATAAATCTTTAAGAGAATATGTT GTTGAACAATATAATCTATAACAGGTACTAAAATTAACAATATATTACAATCCAGATGGAACCTGTTAAGAAGAA GAAATTTAATCATGAGTAAGAAAAGAAAAATAATATTAAGCTTTGGATTATATTTAATTTAATTATTCTTCTAATT CTCTTATTTCTTTTAGGTTTAAGATTAC
Seq3	383	28.2	TGAATCATTTTTAGTTTTGATACTTTTAAAGATAACGACACTACCCAAGAAATTAATGCGCTATAAAGGAAGAGATG ATTTCTGAGCATCGCTAAATCCATTGTAATCGAGGGTGTAGTAAACTGGTAAAACCGAGTTTATAATTAGTTATCT AAATAATCAACGAGTACAATTTAATTATATCAGGGGCTCGTTAGATTTTAAACAAAAATAGCTATAATGATAGGTTTAAA ATCGATGTTTATGATGATATAAGTATAACTGATATTAGACGTGCTGTTTATTAAAAAACATTATTGGAGGCCAAAGAG GATTATAGTTGATGTTAAATATTCTCCAAAAAGAAAAATTATCTGGTAATAAATTATCTATCTTTT
Seq4	365	27.1	AATATCAAACCTAATATATCCATGATACTAATAAAGTTCAAATATAATTGGATTAATTAATCTTTAAAACGTTTAAA AACTTTAAAGCAATTAACCTCAAACCTGAAAAACAAACTGAAAAACAAGAAACAAGAAAGAGCAATATCAATTTG ATTGGAATTCAAATTATGATACCGATGATAATAAATTAATAAAGATATCGCAGTCGTAACCTTAACCCAGGTGCAGT TGTTATTAGCTGTGAGTCCTAACACCTATATTGTCATCTCTAGGTCCTATTGCTGCTCCTCTTGGTTGTAGCTTAAT TAAATAGAAAGGAGAAATAAATGTTAAATAAAGTTCAATTAATAGGTA
Seq5	359	18.1	AAACGTTGGGTTTTATTGGGGCAATTGGACAAATAGTTTTTCAATAAATTTGTAATTTGCTTTATCTATTTTTTATATTTT AACTTTTATTACTTTTTAGTTTTCTTTGATTCTATTTTTCATATCGTTAAGCAAATAAAAAATTATTATTATTGGCCC ATTAACCTTTTAAATTTAGGGATATATGTTTTTTTATTATTATTAATAATTTTATTATTTCCCAAAATCAGAATTAACAA CCAGTTCAAACCTAATAATTCTAATCTAGATGAATTAACAATTAATAAAAAAATATCAGATTTAGAATACAACTTA ATTTACAAAAAACAATAATTAATTAATAAAGTAG

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Table S4. The list of designed LAMP assays selected for experimental evaluation. All the assays were designed on three different genomic sequences, named Seq1, Seq3 and Seq11, specific to AY-SA phytoplasma. Best performing assay, LAMP AY-SA_ftsH, was selected for validation.

Sequence	Assay	Primer name	Primer sequence
Seq1	ID34	TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq1_ID34_F3	CCGAAAAACCATCAAGACCATA
		TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq1_ID34_B3	TTTTGGTTTTGACGAACGT
		TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq1_ID34_FIP*	GGATGAAAAACCTTCGATGTCAAAGAAATCCATACTCATGTTTTGTTTC
		TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq1_ID34_BIP*	ATCTGCCCGTGATATCGAAAAATCATTTTTTATGTCTTGAGTACCTT
	ID77	TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq1_ID77_F3	CCGAAAAACCATCAAGACCATA
		TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq1_ID77_B3	TTTTGGTTTTGACGAACGT
		TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq1_ID77_FIP*	GGATGAAAAACCTTCGATGTCAAAGAATCCATACTCATGTTTTGTTTC
		TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq1_ID77_BIP*	ATCTGCCCGTGATATCGAAAAATCATTTTTTATGTCTTGAGTACCTT
	ID120	TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq1_ID120_F3	CCGAAAAACCATCAAGACCATA
		TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq1_ID120_B3	TTTTGGTTTTGACGAACGT
		TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq1_ID120_FIP*	GGATGAAAAACCTTCGATGTCAAAGAAATCCATACTCATGTTTTGTTTC
		TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq1_ID120_BIP*	ATCTGCCCGTGATATCGAAAAATCATTTTTTATGTCTTGAGTACCTT
	ID163	TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq1_ID163_F3	CCGAAAAACCATCAAGACCATA
		TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq1_ID163_B3	TTTTGGTTTTGACGAACGT
		TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq1_ID163_FIP*	GGATGAAAAACCTTCGATGTCAAAGAATCCATACTCATGTTTTGTTTC
		TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq1_ID163_BIP*	ATCTGCCCGTGATATCGAAAAATCATTTTTTATGTCTTGAGTACCTT
	ID206	TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq1_ID206_F3	CCGAAAAACCATCAAGACCATA
		TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq1_ID206_B3	CTTTTTGGTTTTGACGAACGT
		TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq1_ID206_FIP*	GGATGAAAAACCTTCGATGTCAAAGAAATCCATACTCATGTTTTGTTTC
		TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq1_ID206_BIP*	ATCTGCCCGTGATATCGAAAAATCATTTTTTATGTCTTGAGTACCTT
ID209	TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq1_ID209_F3	CCGAAAAACCATCAAGACCATA	
	TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq1_ID209_B3	CTTTTTGGTTTTGACGAACGT	
	TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq1_ID209_FIP*	GGATGAAAAACCTTCGATGTCAAAGAAATCCATACTCATGTTTTGTTTC	
	TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq1_ID209_BIP*	TCTGCCCGTGATATCGAAAAATCAAATTTTTATGTCTTGAGTACCTT	
ID254	TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq1_ID254_F3	CCGAAAAACCATCAAGACCATA	

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Sequence	Assay	Primer name	Primer sequence
		TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq1_ID254_B3	CTTTTGGTTTTGACGAACGT
		TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq1_ID254_FIP*	GGATGAAAAACCTTCGATGTCAAAGAATCCATACTCATGTTTTGTTTC
		TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq1_ID254_BIP*	CTGCCCGTGATATCGAAAAATCAATATTTTTTATGTCCTGGAGTACCT
	ID30	TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq1_ID30_F3	CCGAAAAACCATCAAGACCATA
		TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq1_ID30_B3	TTGGTTTTGACGAACGTATT
		TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq1_ID30_FIP*	GGATGAAAAACCTTCGATGTCAAAGAAATCCATACTCATGTTTTGTTTC
		TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq1_ID30_BIP*	ATCTGCCCGTGATATCGAAAAATTTTTATGTCCTGGAGTACCTTCT
Seq3	ID4	TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq3_ID4_F3	ACCCAAGAAATTAATAATGGCTAT
		TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq3_ID4_B3	CCAGCACGTCTAATATCAGTT
		TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq3_ID4_FIP*	GGTTTTACCAAGTTTACTAGCACCCAGATGATTTCTGAGCATCGTC
		TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq3_ID4_BIP*	ATCAGGGGCTCGTTAGATTTTAACCATCATAAACATCGATTTTAAACCT
	ID15	TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq3_ID15_F3	ACCCAAGAAATTAATAATGGCTAT
		TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq3_ID15_B3	CCAGCACGTCTAATATCAGT
		TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq3_ID15_FIP*	GGTTTTACCAAGTTTACTAGCACCCAGATGATTTCTGAGCATCGT
		TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq3_ID15_BIP*	ATCAGGGGCTCGTTAGATTTTAACCATCATAAACATCGATTTTAAACCT
	ID17	TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq3_ID17_F3	ACCCAAGAAATTAATAATGGCTAT
		TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq3_ID17_B3	CCAGCACGTCTAATATCAGTT
		TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq3_ID17_FIP*	GGTTTTACCAAGTTTACTAGCACCCGAGATGATTTCTGAGCATCG
		TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq3_ID17_BIP*	ATCAGGGGCTCGTTAGATTTTAACACATCATAAACATCGATTTTAAACCT
	ID27	TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq3_ID27_F3	ACCCAAGAAATTAATAATGGCTAT
		TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq3_ID27_B3	TTTTAATAAACACGACGTCTA
		TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq3_ID27_FIP*	GGTTTTACCAAGTTTACTAGCACCCAGATGATTTCTGAGCATCGT
		TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq3_ID27_BIP*	ATCAGGGGCTCGTTAGATTTTAACCATCATAAACATCGATTTTAAACCT
	ID31	TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq3_ID31_F3	ACCCAAGAAATTAATAATGGCTAT
		TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq3_ID31_B3	TTTTAATAAACACGACGTCTA
		TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq3_ID31_FIP*	GGTTTTACCAAGTTTACTAGCACCCAGATGATTTCTGAGCATCGT
		TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq3_ID31_BIP*	ATCAGGGGCTCGTTAGATTTTAACACATCATAAACATCGATTTTAAACCT

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Seq11	ID24	TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq11_ID24_F3	TGAAGCAGGACACGCTAT
		TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq11_ID24_B3	AATTCTTCAGCCACACGT
		TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq11_ID24_FIP*	CCGAATTTCCACACGGAATAATATTAAGTTGGAACATGCCCA
		TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq11_ID24_BIP*	ATGACACCAGAAACAGAACTTTCTCCCCCTAAATAAGATGTAATTTGG
ID8	ID8	TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq11_ID8_F3	TGAAGCAGGACACGCTAT
		TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq11_ID8_B3	AATTCTTCAGCCACACGT
		TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq11_ID8_FIP*	CCGAATTTCCACACGGAATAATATTAAGTTGGAACATGCCCA
		TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq11_ID8_BIP*	AATGACACCAGAAACAGAACTTTCCCCCTAAATAAGATGTAATTTGG
ID10	ID10	TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq11_ID10_F3	TGAAGCAGGACACGCTAT
		TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq11_ID10_B3	AATTCTTCAGCCACACGT
		TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq11_ID10_FIP*	CCGAATTTCCACACGGAATAATTAAGTTGGAACATGCCCA
		TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq11_ID10_BIP*	AATGACACCAGAAACAGAACTTTCCCCCTAAATAAGATGTAATTTGG
ID55	ID55	TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq11_ID55_F3	TGAAGCAGGACACGCTAT
		TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq11_ID55_B3	CAAAAATTAATTCTTCAGCCACA
		TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq11_ID55_FIP*	CCGAATTTCCACACGGAATAATAAATTAAGTTGGAACATGCCCA
		TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq11_ID55_BIP*	AATGACACCAGAAACAGAACTTTCCGTCCCCCTAAATAAGATGT
AY-SA_ftsH	AY-SA_ftsH	AY-SA_ftsH_F3	TGAAGCAGGACACGCTAT
		AY-SA_ftsH_B3	CAAAAATTAATTCTTCAGCCACA
		AY-SA_ftsH_FIP*	CCGAATTTCCACACGGAATAATTAAGTTGGAACATGCCCA
		AY-SA_ftsH_BIP*	AATGACACCAGAAACAGAACTTTCCGTCCCCCTAAATAAGATGT
ID71	ID71	TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq11_ID71_F3	TGAAGCAGGACACGCTAT
		TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq11_ID71_B3	CAAAAATTAATTCTTCAGCCACA
		TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq11_ID71_FIP*	CCGAATTTCCACACGGAATAATAAATTAAGTTGGAACATGCCCA
		TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq11_ID71_BIP*	ATGACACCAGAAACAGAACTTTCTCGTCCCCCTAAATAAGATGT
ID90	ID90	TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq11_ID90_F3	TGAAGCAGGACACGCTAT
		TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq11_ID90_B3	CAAAAATTAATTCTTCAGCCACA
		TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq11_ID90_FIP*	CCGAATTTCCACACGGAATAATTAAGTTGGAACATGCCCA
		TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq11_ID90_BIP*	TGACACCAGAAACAGAACTTTCTCGTCCCCCTAAATAAGATGT

*All FIP and BIP primers were HPLC cleaned.

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Figure S1. Synthetic target dsDNA standard curve data. Standard curves were performed as two and three technical repeats for LAMP and real-time PCR. A, standard curve for LAMP AY-SA_ftsH assay recorded on QuantStudio 3 Flex real-time PCR systems. B, standard curve for LAMP AY-SA_ftsH assay recorded on QuantStudio 7 Flex real-time PCR systems. C, standard curve for real-time PCR AY-SA_ftsH assay recorded on QuantStudio 3 Flex real-time PCR systems. D, standard curve for real-time PCR AY-SA_ftsH assay recorded on QuantStudio 7 Flex real-time PCR systems. One representative standard curve is shown for each instrument.

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Figure S2. Non-linear modeling of the probability of detection for the AY-SA-specific LAMP (A) and real-time AY-SA-specific PCR assays (B). For both assays two parameter Weibull function fitted the best to experimental data. Log concentration, expressed as $\log(\text{target dsDNA molecules/ml})$; dotted line, 95% probability of detection.

Supplementary File S1

Experimental evaluation an optimisation of AY-SA LAMP assays

Twenty LAMP primer sets were tested empirically using a 30 min amplification at 60, 62 and 65 °C. LAMP assays performance was tested using synthetic target and non-target DNA. For all the LAMP assays. any amplification curve in 30 min was considered a positive reaction.

To determine optimal reaction temperature. LAMP reactions were run at three different temperatures 60, 62 and 65°C. Reaction temperature range was selected based on the optimal temperature activity of GspSSD LF DNA Polymerase used in mastermix (Optigene). The concentration of synthetic DNA template was 5×10^4 molecules/reaction. Specific positive signal was observed for the assays ID55, ID71, ID90 and AY-SA_ftsH (ID 58) at all tested temperatures (Table 1). Other tested assays did not produce any positive signal or exhibited evident cross-reactivity with non-target DNA and/or LAMP reagents. However, on average, the shortest detection time was observed at reaction temperature of 62°C for all the specific assays.

Table 1 Results of experimental evaluation of 20 selected LAMP assays on synthetic target DNA at three different amplification temperatures.

Sequence	Assay	Results of LAMP reaction at different reaction temperature ^a			Characteristic T _m for positive samples
		60 °C	62 °C	65 °C	
Seq.1	ID34	cross reactivity	cross reactivity	cross reactivity	no
	ID77	negative	cross reactivity	cross reactivity	no
	ID120	negative	cross reactivity	cross reactivity	no
	ID163	cross reactivity	cross reactivity	cross reactivity	no
	ID206	cross reactivity	cross reactivity	cross reactivity	no
	ID209	cross reactivity	cross reactivity	cross reactivity	no
	ID254	negative	cross reactivity	cross reactivity	no

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	ID30	cross reactivity	cross reactivity	cross reactivity	no
Seq.3	ID4	negative	negative	cross reactivity	no
	ID15	negative	negative	cross reactivity	no
	ID17	negative	negative	cross reactivity	no
	ID27	negative	negative	cross reactivity	no
	ID31	negative	negative	cross reactivity	no
Seq.11	ID24	cross reactivity	cross reactivity	cross reactivity	no
	ID8	cross reactivity	cross reactivity	cross reactivity	no
	ID10	cross reactivity	cross reactivity	cross reactivity	no
	ID55	positive	positive	positive	yes
	AY-SA_ftsH	positive	positive	positive	yes
	ID71	positive	positive	negative	yes
	ID90	positive	positive	positive	yes

Primer concentration and ratio of the inner and outer primers can affect the speed of the LAMP reaction. The concentration of the outer F3 and B3 primers was maintained at 0.2 μM . Increasing the concentration of the inner primers FIP and BIP resulted in a decrease in time of positivity (Table 2). Optimal primer mixture was considered to contain 1.6 μM FIP and BIP primer, and 0.8 μM F3 and B3 primers. Free Mg^{2+} availability affects primer annealing and DNA polymerase activity, therefore addition of MgCl_2 to reaction mixture was evaluated. Addition of 2 mM MgCl_2 in the LAMP reaction decreased the speed of the LAMP reaction, regardless of the primer concentration. The results were consistent for all 4 tested assays.

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Table 2 Optimization of FIP and BIP primer concentration. Optimal primer concentration was determined based on the shortest time of positivity.

	Time of positivity (min) at FIP/BIP primer concentration*		
	0.8 μ M	1.2 μ M	1.6 μ M
ID55	20.4	20.2	13.9
AY-SA_ftsH	24.3	17.1	16.2
ID71	21.9	20.5	17.7
ID90	21.2	17.0	15.6

*Target DNA concentration was 5×10^4 molecules/reaction.

LAMP reaction does not reach temperatures high enough to facilitate DNA denaturation. Accessibility of double stranded DNA to DNA-polymerase is therefore lower, effecting the speed of the reaction. Time of positivity for heat denatured target DNA was 3 to 4 minutes (3 to 4 cycles) shorter in comparison to double stranded target DNA for all 4 tested assays.

The sensitivity of the developed assay was assessed by testing tenfold serial dilutions of denatured synthetic target sequence qBlock_Seq11 ranging from 10^6 molecules/mL to 10^2 molecules/mL. The results are shown in

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Table 3. LOD of the LAMP assays was in the range of 10^4 to 10^5 target DNA molecules/mL.

Based on the results of optimisation and sensitivity testing, assay AY-SA_ftsH (ID58) was chosen for final optimisation step and validation. In the final optimisation step, the selected LAMP assay was transferred to reaction temperature of 63°C to enable combining LAMP runs with the assays for general phytoplasma detection and detection of different 16Sr groups described by Dickinson (2015). The LAMP assay's performance and reaction characteristics did not change, if reaction temperature was 62°C or 63 °C. Therefore, validation was performed at reaction temperature of 63°C.

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Table 3 Sensitivity of the LAMP assays assessed on synthetic target DNA.

Target sequence conc.	Tp			
	ID55	AY-SA_ftsH	ID71	ID90
1.00E+06	15.1	14.7	19.1	15.0
1.00E+05	16.6	16.7	20.9	17.9
1.00E+04	neg	21.9	neg	neg
1.00E+03	neg	neg	neg	neg
1.00E+02	neg	neg	neg	neg

Reference:

Dickinson, M. 2015. Loop-mediated isothermal amplification (lamp) for detection of phytoplasmas in the field. *Methods Mol. Biol.* 1302:98-111.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 727459

TPS code TrSafe - GY LAMP

Scope of TPS Detection of Grapevine Yellows phytoplasma from South Africa

Report on the results of the test performance study for molecular detection South African aster yellows

Version of report: V1.0

Elaborated by:

Name:	Špela Alič
Organisation:	National Institute of Biology
Date:	17.09.2020

1. INTRODUCTION

Grapevine yellows is a widespread phytoplasma disease. Symptoms of the disease on grapevine caused by AY normally lead to the abortion of immature berries (Engelbrecht et al. 2010) resulting in high levels of yield loss. In South Africa the symptoms of the disease were observed for the first time in 2006. The main agent pathogen causing the South African grapevine yellows (GY) are phytoplasmas classified in 16SrI-B subgroup, corresponding to 'Candidatus Phytoplasma asteris', or Aster Yellows (AY) (Engelbrecht et al., 2010; Carsterns et al., 2011). No permanent cure for AY or other phytoplasma have been reported yet. Therefore, vector control, monitoring and eliminating infected plants represented remain the main management strategy to control the epidemic. Therefore, a novel LAMP test, namely TrSafe_Seq11_ID58 assay, for specific detection of Grapevine Yellows from South Africa was developed and validated in the framework of an EU funded research project, TROPICSAFE (<http://www.tropicsafe.eu/>). The project aims at developing innovative tools and solutions to manage and reduce the impact of these diseases due to insect-transmitted bacteria that are affecting and threatening tropical and subtropical agricultural relevant species. To obtain additional information regarding performance of the novel LAMP assay, interlaboratory comparison through test performance study (TPS) was organised.

National Institute of Biology, Department of Biotechnology and Systems Biology organised the TPS for the detection of Grapevine Aster Yellows from South African (SAAY). Evaluation of the methods was conducted on synthetic DNA and DNA from naturally infected plant matrix.

2. METHODOLOGY AND RESULTS

2.1. Samples

The TPS sample panel was composed of 12 test items: positive samples containing synthetic dsDNA of SAAY, positive samples containing naturally contaminated sample SAAY, and negative samples containing other Aster yellows or host plant *Vitis vinifera* DNA (Table 1). Also, a set of controls were provided.

Stability

Stability of test items and controls was tested with LAMP TrSafe_Seq11_ID58 assay. Stability testing was conducted after results from both participants were obtained. One sample panel and controls stored at < -15 °C were tested in two technical repeats accordingly to TPS protocol. Results were in concordance with the samples target concentration.

Assigned reference values

Reference values were assigned to the test items based on the results of LAMP TrSafe_Seq11_ID58 test (qualitative assigned reference values). Quantitative reference values (target concentrations) were determined for test using digital PCR analysis of test items and controls (Table 1).

Quantitative reference values were determined using LAMP test TrSafe_Seq11_ID58 according to TPS instructions (see 2.3 Methods) prior TPS.

For digital PCR, the real-time PCR TrSafe_Seq11 was transferred to digital PCR format and used to determine the concentration of the target copy numbers in test items and controls. Digital PCR was performed on the QX100™ Droplet Digital™ PCR system (Bio-Rad, Pleasanton, CA, USA). dPCR Supermix for probes (12 µL, Bio-Rad) and 8 µL sample DNA were used, with the primer and probe concentrations of 900 nmol, 900 nmol and 200 nmol per reaction, respectively. After droplet generation, 40 µL of the generated droplet emulsion were transferred to a new 96-well PCR plate (Eppendorf) and amplified in a Thermal Cycler (Bio-Rad). The amplification conditions were 10 min DNA polymerase activation at 95 °C, followed by 45 cycles of a two-step thermal profile of 15 s at 95 °C for denaturation, and 60 s at 60 °C for annealing and extension, followed by a final hold of 10 min at 98 °C for droplet stabilisation and cooling to 4 °C. The temperature ramp rate was set to 3 °C/s, and the lid was heated to 105 °C, according to the Bio-Rad recommendations. After the thermal cycling, the plates were transferred to a droplet reader QX100™ (Bio-Rad). The software package provided with the dPCR system (QuantaSoft™ Software, version 17.4.0917, Bio-Rad) was used for data acquisition. A minimum of 10.000 accepted droplets per reaction was required for the reaction to be considered valid and no non-valid reactions were observed. A fixed manual global threshold discriminating between negative and positive droplets was selected. A reaction was interpreted as positive if the number of positive droplets was ≥ 3 . Positive and no template controls were used in each run. Each sample was analysed in 3 technical repeats. Standard measurement uncertainty was calculated for each sample.

Table 1: Determination of concentrations of target DNA copies in test items and controls with digital PCR. Legend: cps = DNA copies, NA = not applicable.

Sample ID	Sample	Sample description	Digital PCR analysis; 95 % confidence log(cps/mL)*	Contains target?	Expected qualitative result
GY-1	gBlock target	synthetic dsDNA of SAAY	2,6 ± 2,4	yes	positive
GY-2	gBlock target	synthetic dsDNA of SAAY	3,4 ± 2,7	yes	positive
GY-3	gBlock target	synthetic dsDNA of SAAY	4,5 ± 3,8	yes	positive
GY-4	gBlock target	synthetic dsDNA of SAAY	5,6 ± 4,6	yes	positive
GY-5	AY 43(+)	naturally contaminated sample SAAY	5,6 ± 4,6	yes	positive
GY-6	AY 43(+)	naturally contaminated sample SAAY	4,5 ± 3,9	yes	positive
GY-7	Small Bag B(+)	naturally contaminated sample SAAY	5,5 ± 4,6	yes	positive
GY-8	Small Bag B(+)	naturally contaminated sample SAAY	4,4 ± 3,8	yes	positive
GY-9	Small Bag B(+)	naturally contaminated sample SAAY	3,4 ± 2,6	yes	positive
GY-10	D310/17 A	DNA of carrot containing AY (other)	NA	no	negative
GY-11	D322/17 B	DNA of carrot containing AY (other)	NA	no	negative
GY-12	Vitis neg	DNA of Vitis vinifera	NA	no	negative
PAC	PAC	synthetic dsDNA of SAAY	6,5 ± 5,7	yes	positive
NAC	NTC	molecular grade water	NA	no	negative

*Target concentration was measured by digital droplet PCR using TrSafe_Seq11 assay. Measurements were conducted in 3 technical repeats and measurement uncertainty was calculated.

2.2. Consumables

The LAMP primers were provided by the organizer as a mixture and dispatched with the panel. The TPS organizer also provided all the controls needed. The samples were coded in such a way to ensure a blind testing of samples.

2.3. Methods

The organisers supplied the primers, samples and controls (PAC and NAC). The participant had to provide other required reagents, disposables and equipment.

The preliminary studies conducted by the TPS organizer used Isothermal Master Mix ISO 001 (Optigene Ltd., Horsham, UK) as a mastermix.

Table 2: Primers and probe information for test LAMP TrSafe_Seq11_ID58

Oligonucleotides name	Size (nt)	Sequence (5' – 3')
TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq11_ID58_F3	18	TGAAGCAGGACACGCTAT
TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq11_ID58_B3	23	CAAAAATTAATTCTTCAGCCACA
TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq11_ID58_FIP*	40	CCGAATCCACACGGAATAATTAAGTTGGAACATGCCCA
TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq11_ID58_BIP*	45	AATGACACCAGAAACAGAACTTCCGTCCCCCTAAATAAGATGT

*HPLC purified

Experimental protocol

Important: the reaction mixtures should be prepared and kept on ice until analysis (through the addition of sample and control DNA).

Table 3: qPCR mix composition

Reagent (name)	Final concentration/ volume
Isothermal Master Mix ISO 001 (Optigene Ltd., Horsham, UK)	1x
TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq11_ID58_F3	0,20 µM
TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq11_ID58_B3	0,20 µM
TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq11_ID58_FIP	1,60 µM
TrSafe_AY_SA_Seq11_ID58_BIP	1,60 µM
Molecular grade water	/
Volume of the DNA extract	5 µL
Final volume	25 µL

Table 4: LAMP reaction program

LAMP reaction program:	
Amplification	63 °C 30 min
Melting curve	60 - 98 °C, 0.05 °C/s

Note: Each sample and control was analysed in one reaction per strip.

Controls

Controls included:

- **PAC (Positive amplification control):** to monitor the efficiency of the amplification: amplification of nucleic acid of the target organism. This includes nucleic acid isolated from the target organism. A PAC control was provided.
- **NAC (Negative amplification control or no template control):** to rule out false positives due to contamination during the preparation of the reaction mix: amplification of molecular grade water will be provided to prepare the reaction mix.

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Interpretation of results

Verification of the controls:

- NAC should produce no fluorescence or fluorescence with non-characteristic T_m.
- PAC: a positive reaction is defined by a curve of sigmoidal shape above the background, time of positivity below 30 min and T_m in the interval between 82 - 83 °C.

When these conditions are met and controls have valid results, the test is considered valid and the samples interpreted as follows:

- A test is considered positive as defined for PAC reactions (see above).
- A test is considered negative if it produces no fluorescence or fluorescence with non-characteristic T_m.
- Tests should be repeated if any contradictory or unclear results are obtained.
- In case of analysis of duplicate reactions, a test is considered positive if one or more reactions is positive, and negative if both reactions are negative.

2.4. Results

Table 5 Results of the LAMP test TrSafe_Seq11_ID58 evaluated in the TPS. The table presents TPS results of both participants and results of the stability testing. Stability testing was conducted accordingly to TPS protocol after TPS submission of the TPS results. All TPS results were valid and 100 % in concordance with expected results.

Sample ID	Expected qualitative result	Participant						Stability testing		
		1			2			Result stability	Average Tp (min)	Average Tm of positive samples (°C)
		Result	Average Tp (min)	Average Tm of positive samples (°C)	Result	Average Tp (min)	Average Tm of positive samples (°C)			
GY-1 ^a	positive/negative	positive	23.0	82.4	negative	NA	NA	positive	29.0	82.1
GY-2	positive	positive	19.7	82.3	positive	19.9	81.9	positive	23.5	82.2
GY-3	positive	positive	16.5	82.3	positive	15.8	81.8	positive	15.6	82.3
GY-4	positive	positive	13.7	82.3	positive	13.3	82.0	positive	12.9	82.3
GY-5	positive	positive	13.2	82.2	positive	13.6	82.1	positive	13.3	82.2
GY-6	positive	positive	15.8	82.3	positive	15.7	82.1	positive	15.3	82.3
GY-7	positive	positive	13.7	82.3	positive	13.2	81.9	positive	13.7	82.3
GY-8	positive	positive	16.2	82.3	positive	15.7	82.0	positive	16.1	82.4
GY-9	positive	positive	19.8	82.1	positive	17.3	82.2	positive	23.0	82.1
GY-10	negative	negative	NA	NA	negative	NA	NA	negative	NA	NA
GY-11	negative	negative	NA	NA	negative	NA	NA	negative	NA	NA
GY-12	negative	negative	NA	NA	negative	NA	NA	negative	NA	NA
PAC	positive	positive	11.9	82.2	positive	11.7	82.1	positive	11.4	82.2
NAC	negative	negative	NA	NA	negative	NA	NA	negative	NA	NA

^aTarget concentration in the sample GY-1 was at the limit of detection (LOD) of the LAMP test, therefore either, positive or negative results were expected.

The controls provided with the test panel were used as a quality check of the data set. If both controls results were concordant with the expected results, test panel data was considered as valid. All TPS results were valid and 100 % in concordance with expected results. Target concentration in the sample GY-1 was at the limit of detection (LOD) of the LAMP test, therefore either, positive or negative results were expected.

Analytical specificity

LAMP test TrSafe_Seq11_ID58 was designed to specifically detect only Aster yellows phytoplasma from South Africa. Two test item were comprised of naturally infected carrot samples with aster yellows phytoplasma and one test item contained DNA of healthy host plant *Vitis vinifera*. The TPS confirmed that the LAMP test TrSafe_Seq11_ID58 does not cross react with other Aster yellow phytoplasma or host plant DNA.

Analytical sensitivity of the test determined synthetic dsDNA of SAAY

The analytical sensitivity of the tests was determined on serial dilution of synthetic target DNA. Each test panel contained PAC, GY-4, GY-3, GY-2 and GY-1 test items that formed 10 fold serial dilutions ranging from 6.5 to 2.6 log(copies/mL). Results of those sample items were used to determine limit of detection by non-linear modelling. Synthetic dsDNA samples did not contain any host background DNA.

Based on the results, host DNA does not affect sensitivity of the LAMP test.

For non-linear modelling of the TPS results, the best fit models for the test were two-parameter Weibull function (W2.2) and asymptotic regression (AR.2). The concentration (log(copies/mL) detected with 95 % probability is shown in Figure 1 (written in red).

Figure 1 Non-linear modelling of probability of detection for LAMP test TrSafe_Seq11_ID58. The Left model shows probability of detection determined on serial dilution of synthetic target DNA without host background and the right model shows probability of detection for dilution of naturally contaminated sample SAAY. Concentrations shown are expressed as log(copies/mL) and were measured by digital PCR assay.

Legend: W2.2 = two-parameter Weibull function; AR.2 = asymptotic regression. The dotted line denotes 95 % probability of detection

3. CONCLUSION

The scope of this TPS was detection of South African Aster yellows using LAMP test TrSafe_Seq11_ID58. The following can be concluded based on the results of the TPS:

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- Newly developed LAMP test TrSafe_Seq11_ID58 showed high sensitivity on synthetic dsDNA of SAAY and naturally contaminated samples SAAY.
- LAMP test TrSafe_Seq11_ID58 does not cross react with other tested Aster yellow phytoplasma or *Vitis vinifera* host plant DNA.

4. REFERENCES

Engelbrecht, M., Joubert, J., & Burger, J. T. (2010). First report of aster yellows phytoplasma in grapevines in South Africa. *Plant disease*, *94*(3), 373-373.

Carstens, R. (2014). *The incidence and distribution of grapevine yellows disease in South African vineyards* (Doctoral dissertation, Stellenbosch: Stellenbosch University).

Nicolaisen, M., Dermastia, M., Dreo, T., Alič, Š., Contaldo, N., Satta, E., Bertaccini, A., Dickinson, M., Angelini, E., Burger, J., Campa, M., Pietersen, G., Formica, L., Pietersen, G., Oropeza, C., Narvaez, M., Yankey, N. (2019). New diagnostic protocols (LAMP and ELISA, lateral flow) for detection of GY, LY and HLB : deliverable number D4.3 : work package WP4.

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5. APPENDENCES

5.1. Appendix 1: Gene Experiment report – participant 1, run 1

Genie Experiment Report

Profile Name	
Start Time	13:01:58 - petek, 14. avgust 2020
End Time	13:45:25 - petek, 14. avgust 2020
Serial Number	GEN2-1047

Preheat	No
Temperature	45 °C
Time	3 min(s)

Isothermal	Yes
Temperature	63 °C
Time	30 min
Gradient	0 °C

Anneal	Yes
Start Temp	98 °C
End Temp	60 °C
Ramp Rate	0,05 °C/sec

Estimated Run time	43:58 (mm:ss)
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Advanced Options:

Preheat Ramp Rate	1 °C/Sec
Isothermal Ramp Rate	1 °C/Sec
Isothermal period	15 Sec
Anneal initial rate	1 °C/Sec
Anneal period	0 Sec
Anneal settling time	5 Sec

Notes:

Smoothing Points	3	Normalization	From =0 sec To =180 sec
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Smoothing Points	2
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Peak	Width	Threshold
Simple	0(Sec)	0,02(ratio)

Well Number	Well Name(mm:ss)	Peak Value(mm:ss)
1	Sample1 (GY-11)	02:00
2	Sample 2 (GY-12)	
3	Sample 3 (GY-2)	01:45
4	Sample 4 (GY-4)	01:45
5	Sample 5 (GY-5)	13:15
6	Sample 6 (GY-6)	02:00
7	PAC	11:45
8	NAC	
9	Sample 7 (GY-7)	13:45
10	Sample 8 (GY-1)	
11	Sample 9 (GY-3)	01:45
12	Sample 10 (GY-8)	02:00
13	Sample 11 (GY-9)	02:15
14	Sample 12 (GY-10)	02:00
15	PAC[15]	01:45
16	NAC[16]	02:45

Smoothing Points

3

Smoothing Points	2
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Peak	Width	Threshold
Simple	4(mm:ss)	5000

Well Number	Well Name(°C)	Peak Value(°C)
1	Sample1 (GY-11)	
2	Sample 2 (GY-12)	
3	Sample 3 (GY-2)	82,3
4	Sample 4 (GY-4)	82,3
5	Sample 5 (GY-5)	82,2
6	Sample 6 (GY-6)	82,2
7	PAC	82,1
8	NAC	
9	Sample 7 (GY-7)	82,3
10	Sample 8 (GY-1)	82,3
11	Sample 9 (GY-3)	82,2
12	Sample 10 (GY-8)	82,3
13	Sample 11 (GY-9)	82,1
14	Sample 12 (GY-10)	
15	PAC[15]	82,1
16	NAC[16]	

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5.2 Appendix 2: Gene Experiment report – participant 1, run 2

Genie Experiment Report

Profile Name	
Start Time	14:05:19 - petek, 14. avgust 2020
End Time	14:48:43 - petek, 14. avgust 2020
Serial Number	GEN2-1047

Preheat	No
Temperature	45 °C
Time	3 min(s)

Isothermal	Yes
Temperature	63 °C
Time	30 min
Gradient	0 °C

Anneal	Yes
Start Temp	98 °C
End Temp	60 °C
Ramp Rate	0,05 °C/sec

Estimated Run time	43:58 (mm:ss)
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Advanced Options:

Preheat Ramp Rate	1 °C/Sec
Isothermal Ramp Rate	1 °C/Sec
Isothermal period	15 Sec
Anneal initial rate	1 °C/Sec
Anneal period	0 Sec
Anneal settling time	5 Sec

Notes:

Smoothing Points	3	Normalization	From =0 sec To =180 sec
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Smoothing Points	2
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Peak	Width	Threshold
Simple	0(Sec)	0,02(ratio)

Well Number	Well Name(mm:ss)	Peak Value(mm:ss)
1	Sample 1 (GY-11)	
2	Sample 2 (GY-12)	
3	Sample 3 (GY-2)	17:30
4	Sample 4 (GY-4)	13:45
5	Sample (GY-5)	13:15
6	Sample 6 (GY-6)	02:30
7	PAC	12:00
8	NAC	
9	Sample 7 (GY-7)	01:45
10	Sample 8 (GY-1)	
11	Sample 9 (GY-3)	16:00
12	Sample 10 (GY-8)	15:45
13	Sample 11 (GY-9)	19:30
14	Sample 12 (GY-10)	
15	PAC[15]	11:45
16	NAC[16]	

Smoothing Points	3
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Smoothing Points	2
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Peak	Width	Threshold
Simple	4(mm:ss)	5000

Well Number	Well Name(°C)	Peak Value(°C)
1	Sample 1 (GY-11)	
2	Sample 2 (GY-12)	
3	Sample 3 (GY-2)	82,2
4	Sample 4 (GY-4)	82,3
5	Sample (GY-5)	82,2
6	Sample 6 (GY-6)	82,3
7	PAC	82,2
8	NAC	
9	Sample 7 (GY-7)	82,3
10	Sample 8 (GY-1)	
11	Sample 9 (GY-3)	82,3
12	Sample 10 (GY-8)	82,4
13	Sample 11 (GY-9)	82,1
14	Sample 12 (GY-10)	
15	PAC[15]	82,2
16	NAC[16]	

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5.3 Appendix 3: Gene Experiment report – participant 2, run 1

Genie Experiment Report

Profile Name	tropicsafe gy samples test 1 matt
Start Time	11:48:40 - 10 August 2020
End Time	12:28:00 - 10 August 2020
Serial Number	GEN2-1040

Preheat	No
Temperature	45 °C
Time	3 min(s)

Isothermal	Yes
Temperature	63 °C
Time	30 min
Gradient	0 °C

Anneal	Yes
Start Temp	98 °C
End Temp	70 °C
Ramp Rate	0.05 °C/sec

Estimated Run time	41:33 (mm:ss)
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Advanced Options:

Preheat Ramp Rate	1 °C/Sec
Isothermal Ramp Rate	1 °C/Sec
Isothermal period	15 Sec
Anneal initial rate	1 °C/Sec
Anneal period	0 Sec
Anneal settling time	60 Sec

Notes:

Smoothing Points	3	Normalization	From =0 sec To =180 sec
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Smoothing Points	2
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Peak	Width	Threshold
Simple	0(Sec)	0.02(ratio)

Well Number	Well Name(mm:ss)	Peak Value(mm:ss)
1	well1	
2	well2	
3	well3	16:30
4	well4	13:45
5	well5	14:00
6	well6	16:30
7	well7	02:45
8	well8	
9	well9	13:30
10	well10	16:30
11	well11	
12	well12	
13	well13	
14	well14	
15	well15	12:00
16	well16	

Smoothing Points	3
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Smoothing Points	2
-------------------------	---

Peak	Width	Threshold
Simple	4(mm:ss)	5000

Well Number	Well Name(°C)	Peak Value(°C)
1	well1	
2	well2	81.8
3	well3	81.8
4	well4	81.9
5	well5	82.0
6	well6	82.0
7	well7	82.0
8	well8	
9	well9	81.9
10	well10	82.0
11	well11	
12	well12	
13	well13	
14	well14	
15	well15	82.1
16	well16	

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5.4 Appendix 4: Gene Experiment report – participant 2, run 2

Genie Experiment Report

Profile Name	SLOVENIA TEST
Start Time	13:38:21 - 11 August 2020
End Time	14:16:24 - 11 August 2020
Serial Number	GEN2-1040

Preheat	No
Temperature	45 °C
Time	3 min(s)

Isothermal	Yes
Temperature	63 °C
Time	30 min
Gradient	0 °C

Anneal	Yes
Start Temp	98 °C
End Temp	80 °C
Ramp Rate	0.05 °C/sec

Estimated Run time	38:13 (mm:ss)
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Advanced Options:

Preheat Ramp Rate	1 °C/Sec
Isothermal Ramp Rate	1 °C/Sec
Isothermal period	15 Sec
Anneal initial rate	1 °C/Sec
Anneal period	0 Sec
Anneal settling time	60 Sec

Notes:

Smoothing Points	3	Normalization	From =0 sec To =180 sec
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Smoothing Points	2
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Peak	Width	Threshold
Simple	0(Sec)	0.02(ratio)

Well Number	Well Name(mm:ss)	Peak Value(mm:ss)
1	GY-1	
2	GY-2	
3	GY-3	15:30
4	GY-4	13:15
5	GY-5	13:15
6	GY-6	15:00
7	PAC	11:15
8	NAC	
9	GY-7	13:15
10	GY-8	15:00
11	GY-9	17:30
12	GY-10	
13	GY-11	
14	GY-12	
15	PAC[15]	11:45
16	NAC[16]	

Smoothing Points	3
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Smoothing Points	2
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Peak	Width	Threshold
Simple	4(mm:ss)	5000

Well Number	Well Name(°C)	Peak Value(°C)
1	GY-1	
2	GY-2	82.0
3	GY-3	81.9
4	GY-4	82.0
5	GY-5	82.1
6	GY-6	82.1
7	PAC	82.1
8	NAC	
9	GY-7	81.9
10	GY-8	82.0
11	GY-9	82.2
12	GY-10	
13	GY-11	
14	GY-12	
15	PAC[15]	82.0
16	NAC[16]	

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5.5 Appendix 5: Gene Experiment report – stability testing, run 1

Genie Experiment Report

Profile Name	
Start Time	16:16:29 - četrtek, 27. avgust 2020
End Time	16:59:58 - četrtek, 27. avgust 2020
Serial Number	GEN2-1047

Preheat	No
Temperature	45 °C
Time	3 min(s)

Isothermal	Yes
Temperature	63 °C
Time	30 min
Gradient	0 °C

Anneal	Yes
Start Temp	98 °C
End Temp	60 °C
Ramp Rate	0,05 °C/sec

Estimated Run time	43:58 (mm:ss)
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Advanced Options:

Preheat Ramp Rate	1 °C/Sec
Isothermal Ramp Rate	1 °C/Sec
Isothermal period	15 Sec
Anneal initial rate	1 °C/Sec
Anneal period	0 Sec
Anneal settling time	5 Sec

Notes:

Smoothing Points	3	Normalization	From =0 sec To =180 sec
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Smoothing Points	2
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Peak	Width	Threshold
Simple	0(Sec)	0,02(ratio)

Well Number	Well Name(mm:ss)	Peak Value(mm:ss)
1	GY-1	01:45
2	GY-2	01:45
3	GY-3	01:45
4	GY-4	02:15
5	GY-5	13:15
6	GY-6	15:30
7	PAC	01:45
8	NAC	
9	GY-7	14:15
10	GY-8	16:15
11	GY-9	03:00
12	GY-10	03:00
13	GY-11	02:30
14	GY-12	02:00
15	PAC[15]	03:00
16	NAC[16]	

Smoothing Points	3
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Smoothing Points	2
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Peak	Width	Threshold
Simple	4(mm:ss)	5000

Well Number	Well Name(°C)	Peak Value(°C)
1	GY-1	
2	GY-2	82,2
3	GY-3	82,3
4	GY-4	82,3
5	GY-5	82,2
6	GY-6	82,2
7	PAC	82,1
8	NAC	
9	GY-7	82,3
10	GY-8	82,3
11	GY-9	82,0
12	GY-10	
13	GY-11	
14	GY-12	
15	PAC[15]	82,2
16	NAC[16]	

Report on the results of the test performance study for molecular detection South African aster yellows, v1.0, Tropicsafe, GA n°727459. National Institute of Biology, Ljubljana, 2020.

5.6 Appendix 5: Gene Experiment report – stability testing, run 2

Genie Experiment Report

Profile Name	
Start Time	17:38:30 - četrtek, 27. avgust 2020
End Time	18:21:55 - četrtek, 27. avgust 2020
Serial Number	GEN2-1047

Preheat	No
Temperature	45 °C
Time	3 min(s)

Isothermal	Yes
Temperature	63 °C
Time	30 min
Gradient	0 °C

Anneal	Yes
Start Temp	98 °C
End Temp	60 °C
Ramp Rate	0,05 °C/sec

Estimated Run time	43:58 (mm:ss)
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Advanced Options:

Preheat Ramp Rate	1 °C/Sec
Isothermal Ramp Rate	1 °C/Sec
Isothermal period	15 Sec
Anneal initial rate	1 °C/Sec
Anneal period	0 Sec
Anneal settling time	5 Sec

Notes:

Smoothing Points	3	Normalization	From =0 sec To =180 sec
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Smoothing Points	2
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Peak	Width	Threshold
Simple	0(Sec)	0,02(ratio)

Well Number	Well Name(mm:ss)	Peak Value(mm:ss)
1	GY-1	02:00
2	GY-2	02:30
3	GY-3	15:15
4	GY-4	13:45
5	GY-5	13:45
6	GY-6	02:30
7	PAC	02:15
8	NAC	
9	GY-7	13:15
10	GY-8	16:00
11	GY-9	20:30
12	GY-10	
13	GY-11	
14	GY-12	
15	PAC[15]	12:00
16	NAC[16]	

Smoothing Points

3

Smoothing Points	2
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Peak	Width	Threshold
Simple	4(mm:ss)	5000

Well Number	Well Name(°C)	Peak Value(°C)
1	GY-1	82,1
2	GY-2	82,3
3	GY-3	82,3
4	GY-4	82,3
5	GY-5	82,2
6	GY-6	82,3
7	PAC	82,2
8	NAC	
9	GY-7	82,3
10	GY-8	82,4
11	GY-9	82,2
12	GY-10	
13	GY-11	
14	GY-12	
15	PAC[15]	82,2
16	NAC[16]	